

**Title: Submerged Sensor Localization Using Cayley-Menger
Determinant with Diverse Equations and Security**

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Abstract

This thesis introduces a novel approach for underwater sensor localization by employing a static configuration of six surface beacons arranged in a pentagonal formation. This spatial arrangement effectively mitigates singularity issues in the Cayley-Menger determinant which typically arise in co-linear or co-planar configurations to ensure accurate and reliable position estimation. The proposed method incorporates real-time filtering techniques to account for minor sensor displacements caused by ocean currents or sinking to enhance the localization system's robustness. The predictive model utilizes machine learning algorithms such as Linear Regression, Random Forest, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), is employed to estimate the future positions of submerged sensors while compensating for the dynamic effects of ocean currents. Additionally, this thesis evaluates the acoustic speed using multiple empirical formulas—Mackenzie, Medwin, Chen–Millero, Wilson, Leroy, Coppens, and Del Grosso—each tailored to different environmental conditions, ensuring precise distance measurement and mitigating inaccuracies in position estimation. The effect of three environmental factors has been measured and analyzed in detailed. Furthermore, security concerns related to underwater sensor networks are addressed through the development of jamming detection protocols which will ensure reliable communication despite the challenging nature of underwater acoustic environments. This comprehensive approach provides a scalable, accurate, and efficient solution for underwater sensor localization and monitoring also offering significant advancements in submerged sensor tracking and marine research under dynamic and variable oceanic conditions.

Declaration

We hereby announce that this project was completed under CSE400 and has not been submitted elsewhere for the requirement of any degree or diploma or for any purpose except for publication.

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Letter of Acceptance

We hereby declare that this thesis is from the students' work and best effort of mine, and all other sources of information used have been acknowledged. This thesis has been submitted with our approval.

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Abbreviation and Acronyms

UWSN	Underwater Wireless Sensor Network
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network
GPS	Global Positioning System
NDLP	Node Discovery and Localization Protocol
ALS	Area Localization Scheme
MLSL	Maximum-likelihood Source Localization Approach
LPS	Local Positioning System
RF	Radio Frequency
TDOA	Time Difference of Arrival
TOA	Time of Arrival
RTOA	Round Trip Time of Arrival
AUV	Autonomous Underwater Vehicles
UUV	Unnamed Underwater Vehicles
SVP	Sound Velocity Profile
CMD	Cayley-Menger determinant
UWJDP	Underwater Jamming Detection Protocol

PSR	Packet Send Ratio
PDR	Packet Delivery Ratio
ECA	Energy Consumption Amount

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 About Underwater Wireless Network

The Underwater Wireless Sensor Network has been one of the interesting and prominent sectors of research among researchers for decades. Essentially, Underwater wireless sensor networks or UWSNs are primarily made up of sensor nodes that collect and communicate data via wireless communication beneath the water's surface. In the 1960's the researchers initially developed acoustic communication for military purposes. Underwater wireless networking systems or "UWSN" have been popular for many reasons, one of them being ocean life exploration. There are also several reasons like natural disaster detection, military underwater surveillance, quality detection of water, marine creature study or we can say marine biology, oceanography, many types of industrial applications, navigation, and for monitoring the underwater environment etc. UWSN is one of the primary technologies for research for not only communication purposes but also for so many reasons. Many applications use this for gathering data and analysis purposes but if we do not know its location from where the data is obtained all of this will be of no use. Underwater wireless communication is still a very challenging term as radio signals cannot go very deep, mainly this type of network is designed for the marine environment not mandatorily because of the saline water the passing of the signal and the movement is already a little difficult. Instead of RS (Radio Signal), we use acoustic signals. For the proper understanding of the actuation data appropriate sensor localization is essential. Unfortunately, the distinctive features of underwater acoustic channels include extended propagation delays, restricted bandwidth, motion-induced Doppler shift, multipath interference, and so forth.

1.2 Techniques used for localization in UWSN

Recent advancements in technology have spurred the development of innovative methods for overcoming the inherent challenges of UWSNs. We have focused on the Cayle Menger determinant to do the localization and done to the work by advancement is the integration of localization techniques with machine learning (ML) offering a promising solution for improving

accuracy and efficiency in underwater sensor networks. The localization process particularly in underwater environments is highly complex due to the dynamic nature of aquatic conditions such as varying water currents, temperature gradients, and salinity. These factors can impact the accuracy of traditional localization methods necessitating the use of robust mathematical models like the Cayley-Menger determinant. This determinant widely recognized in distance geometry provides a foundation for calculating precise locations by leveraging geometric relationships between sensor nodes. When coupled with ML algorithms this approach enhances adaptability and accuracy by learning from environmental data and optimizing localization strategies in real time.

1.3 About the Acoustic Channels

The meaning of ‘acoustic’ stands for science which deals with reception, production, transmission and effects of sound. Many applications use acoustic signals, for example sonar navigation systems to locate submarines or ships, underwater communications, oceanographic data collection and monitoring. Originally it is the understanding of small pressure on air which the human ear can detect or listen. At present the structural vibration is considered a part of acoustic. We will conclude our introduction with the primary definition and to the spread to fluid identically to air and water. In that case we can say acoustics can be considered as a part of fluid dynamics [1]. At present time acoustic channels in underwater environments for communication are very difficult mediums to use. For acoustic propagation it is generally supported in low frequency and with limited bandwidth. As history suggests, a significant development in signal processing can be achieved whenever the physical behavior of the propagation were recognized by reliable channel modeling [2]. A considerable complication with fluid mechanics is that the equations of transit are nonlinear. Acoustic transmission has three characterizations which are,

- Attenuation which usually depends on the signal frequency,
- Multipath propagation,
- Low speed of velocity which is around 1500 m/s.

Acoustics are contemplates of first order estimation where nonlinear effects are negligible. Traditionally, the generation of acoustic sounds is thought to be a boundary box problem. Loudspeakers generated sound or any type of unsteady movement on solid boundaries can be considered as a sound generation process in traditional acoustic [1].

1.4 Historical Perspective in Underwater Acoustic Communications & Networking

The first prosperous estimation of velocity of sound was done at the beginning of the 1800s where researchers used a tube for listing underwater which was suggested by the famous artist Da Vinci and scientists recorded the speed of the submerged bell proceeding across Lake Geneva [3]. Underwater communications using acoustic signals were used to communicate with the submarines. The 'Gertude' or we can say marine telephone was invented for audio transmission. It uses analog modulation and its carrier frequency was between 2 kHz to 15 kHz and this type of hardware is still found in military submarines or even in systemic submersibles like Alvin. Williams and Battestin explained the feature of the acoustic medium which was the temporal consistency and that was high enough for channel estimation and consequent benefit. Almost 40 years after this invention other researchers have found more advanced processing techniques for channel estimation and they also have implemented algorithms on electronic computers, but the core technique demonstrated here was the same as the seminal work [4].

1.5 Techniques of Solving Average Speed Measurement of Acoustic Signal and analyzing the effect of environmental factors

In this work we are inserted into the measurement of acoustic velocity which is influenced by different factors in the underwater environment using different empirical equations and also, we will find out which environmental parameter does have a high effect on the speed of sound (Using Mackenzie equation). In chapter 3 section 3.5 we have discussed it in detail.

The three main variables of the environment are considered temperature, depth and salinity and these are also considered as the function of underwater speed. With the help of distance measurement techniques, the Navy has developed various tools which can be used for communication underwater or for monitoring the environment.

1.6 Security threats in Underwater Wireless Sensor Network

UWSN and physical WSN both consist of structural sensors or equipment which can monitor its surroundings and collect data which can be used in different tasks. This technology has gained popularity over the years and at present it has become a part of our daily lives [5]. UWSN network faces a lot of unique challenges like slow transmission speed, rough environment to communicate, limited power source to operate, node mobility and because of these challenges the network

become very fragile to various security threats for example

Jamming, Denial-of-Service (DoS) and sybil attack [6]. According to the attack times cyber threats can be divided into two sectors [7]

- Passive attack: The goal of this attack is to analyze the traffic of the network without interrupting communication. Here the attacker does not disturb the process of the nodes but to examine the process. These types of attacks are difficult to detect.
- Active attack: The attacker objective here is to tamper, inject malicious packets on the network and disturbs the communication method of the network. This type of attack is difficult to prevent.

DoS attack is one of the active attacks and jamming attack is a type of Dos attack.

In this thesis we are interested in jamming detection. In jamming attacks usually, the hacker injects unnecessary packets on the communication media so that the communication channel is not able to transmit any information. Jamming attacks are considered very significant because of three reasons [5]

- Jamming attack can be done by only listening to the open communication channel and then broadcasting packets on the network
- This attack damages the whole network and decreases its performance over time with a minimal cost by attackers.
- For jamming attacks no special or expensive devices or hardware are recruited.

There are many types of strategies jammers can use to interfere in wireless communication. As the attacker has different types of philosophies, these different attack models also has different levels of impact on the UWSN [8].

1.7 Different Matrices for Jamming Detection

Jamming detection can be done using various types of parameters such as CST, PSR, PDR, ECA, SDRSS, RSS, SNR and so on. In this work we will use PSR, PDR and ECA to detect the jamming event [9]. It is discussed in chapter - 3 section 3.6. We implemented the proposed UWJDP in [26] and these three parameters are used for detection because of their simplicity which help to determine whether it is jammed or not.

1.8 Research Questions of our thesis

In our thesis we have focused on different techniques related to the improvement of Underwater Wireless Sensor Network. For any network, especially for wireless network we need to know the precise position of the device or node which are the part of the network. Also, in underwater we use acoustic signals to communication and environment factors has a great effect on it and also cyber-attack are a major use with wireless network. Based on these focuses our research questions can be formed as,

- What would be the most effective technique for UWSN localization?
- How can Machine Learning play a vital role in predicting future position in UWSN?
- Why do we use Acoustic signals in UWSN?
- How can we determine the acoustic speed of underwater vertical columns?
- What environmental parameter has the most effect on the acoustic signal?
- What to do if any security threats are introduced to our UWSN?

1.9 Object of our thesis work

Our work is focused on development of UWSN and for that we have investigated and also solved related problem filed which are used in the development of underwater networking. It has been a prominent sector of research for decades. As we mentioned earlier, we have investigated different problem fields related to UWSN so we can define the objective of this work as

- Applying Cayley-Menger Determination to solve the localization problem and also propose a more effective configuration for CMD to able to work in dynamic environment
- Machine Learning techniques like Linear regression and RNN to predict the future coordinates of the sensors which can be helpful for sensor monitoring and other real time work.
- Acoustic signal properties determination of acoustic signal speed using different empirical formulas.
- Analyze the effect of three environmental factors, temperature, depth and salinity on the acoustic signal velocity.
- Implementation of UWJDP and see its workflow to understand how we can establish a secure communication network.

1.10 Significance of our Work

Our thesis works are considering all the aspects of establishing a UWSN. We have done sensor localization using CMD and proposed a pentagon shape while taking the measurement which helps to achieve dynamicity. Acoustic signals are used in the marine environment as they have a large propagation range. To determine the distance of the node we usually use $d = v \times t$ and where v is the acoustic speed but in underwater there are different parameters which affect the acoustic signal which can be measured using empirical equation and for better understanding we also find the effect of environmental factors on the velocity of the sound.

And for our network architecture we have implemented a jamming protocol.

So, we can say we have navigated almost all the significant sectors of UWSN.

1.11 Proposed Method

The proposed method addresses the challenges in underwater sensor localization by employing a configuration of six surface beacons arranged in a pentagonal shape. This spatial arrangement ensures that the beacons are non-co-linear or non-co-planar which effectively mitigate singularity issues in the CMD. Singularity issues arise due to collinear or coplanar configurations. The Cayley-Menger determinant is a mathematical tool used to calculate distances and verify geometric properties in multi-dimensional spaces. CMD is particularly effective for underwater localization as it enables the precise determination of relative positions by solving for unknown coordinates from known inter-beacon distances [10,11,12]. However, singularities in the determinant can compromise the accuracy of localization which is why optimal beacon placement is critical [1]. By adopting the pentagonal arrangement this method minimizes these singular conditions providing a robust framework for submerged sensor tracking. In [11], only one beacon node is considered on the surface of the water and three sensor nodes are situated at the underwater level which is in a parallel plane with the surface of the water. Unlike traditional methods requiring the repositioning of a single beacon assuming the sensor remains relatively static during this interval [12], this static configuration allows for rapid data acquisition in milliseconds. This approach ensures precise and reliable localization even under challenging underwater conditions eliminating the inefficiencies associated with moving beacons and enabling real-time monitoring of submerged sensors.

To account for the dynamic effects of ocean currents this study also incorporates predictive modeling to estimate the future positions of the submerged sensor. Data from 50 iterations were collected to observe the gradual movement of the lost sensor under the influence of ocean currents. Machine learning models including Linear Regression, Random Forest, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) were employed and compared for their ability to predict the sensor's future locations. Linear Regression served as a baseline for capturing linear trends in the sensor's motion but failed to model complex temporal dependencies [16]. Random Forest enhanced prediction accuracy by capturing non-linear relationships yet its independence assumption for data points limited its performance in a time-series context [17,18]. Recurrent Neural Networks demonstrated the best predictive capabilities by learning temporal dependencies inherent in the sequential data. These models effectively predicted the sensor's trajectory adapting to variations in current strengths and directions [20]. This predictive approach enhances real-time localization by compensating for the sensor's motion making it particularly suited for dynamic underwater environments [21]. The results validate the effectiveness of this method by marking significant progress in submerged sensor tracking under variable oceanic conditions.

To ensure precise distance measurement in underwater environments the proposed method incorporates an evaluation of the acoustic speed using multiple empirical formulas accounting for variations in temperature, salinity, and depth. Accurate modeling of sound speed is critical for underwater localization as errors in acoustic speed can propagate into significant inaccuracies in position estimation. The influence of environmental factors on underwater acoustic propagation has been extensively analyzed in prior studies. In this work the Mackenzie, Medwin, Chen–Millero, Wilson, Leroy, Coppens, and Del Grosso formulas are applied to compute sound speed. Each formula offers distinct methodologies and levels of precision tailored to specific conditions. For example, the Mackenzie formula is widely used for its simplicity while the Del Grosso and Chen–Millero formulas provide high accuracy by considering complex thermodynamic properties. Coppens' formula is particularly suited for shallow water environments which are often encountered in practical applications. Comparative analysis of the calculated sound speed values reveals notable differences under varying environmental conditions emphasizing the importance of formula selection in ensuring localization reliability. For instance, Medwin's formula simplifies acoustic speed calculation for average ocean conditions whereas Leroy's approach integrates higher-order corrections for salinity and temperature dependencies. This comparative study further

validates the importance of using in-situ data for selecting the most appropriate empirical model. Incorporating these insights ensures robust localization by mitigating the effects of environmental variations on distance measurements aligning with findings from recent acoustic speed research. **[22,18,16]**

Underwater sensor networks (UWSNs) are highly susceptible to jamming attacks and interference due to the challenging nature of underwater acoustic communication. Misra et al. **[9]** proposed the Underwater Jamming Detection Protocol (UWJDP), which leverages packet delivery ratio (PDR) thresholds to detect jamming and isolate affected regions ensuring the reliability of communication. Foundational research by Akyildiz et al. **[9]** and Sozer et al. **[27]** highlights the complexities of underwater communication, emphasizing the impact of signal attenuation and interference. These studies collectively inform the development of robust protocols such as UWJD tailored to address the unique challenges of underwater environments, enhancing sensor localization and communication security.

Chapter 2

Literature review:

The collection of papers presents diverse approaches to underwater sensor localization addressing challenges like mobility, environmental factors, and synchronization. Rahman (2020) and Rahman et al. (2018) explore the use of the Cayley-Menger determinant (CMD) and single beacons for precise localization. Tan et al. (2011) review methods including TOA/AOA and environmental impacts while Zhou et al. (2011) focus on mobility-based improvements. Other studies like those by Luo et al. (2010) and Kantarci et al. (2007) highlight the use of directional beacons and AUVs for enhancing localization. Researchers such as Paul et al. (2020) integrate advanced mathematical functions like Lambert-W for real-time mobile sensor localization. The use of machine learning techniques such as Random Forests (Breiman, 2001) and LSTMs (Hochreiter & Schmidhuber, 1997), also appears in these works, contributing to predictions and trajectory forecasting in dynamic underwater conditions. Furthermore, studies on time synchronization (Syed & Heidemann, 2006) and environmental factors affecting sound speed (Rahman, 2013) underscore the importance of precision in underwater networks.

The table below provides a comprehensive summary of the related work and includes their performed work, findings, and contributions.

Table No: 01

Reference and year	Author	Perform work	Findings and contribution
[10], 2020	A. Rahman	Non-Parallelism and Cayley-Menger Determinant in Submerged Localization	Addresses the limitations of using the CMD for submerged node localization in non-parallel states, proposing a model for accurate positioning through precise distance measurements.
[41], 2011	H.-P.Tan,R. Diamant, W. K. G. Seah, and M. Waldmeyer	A survey of techniques and challenges in underwater localization	This paper compares underwater approaches like range-based, range-free, and hybrid techniques. Here, ranged base localization uses TOA or AOA to measure distances. It also analys underwater challenges like

			<p>multipath fading, limited bandwidth and high latency also underwater variables like temperature, depth and salinity affect the accuracy of underwater localization.</p>
[11], 2013	A. Rahman, V. Muthukkumarasamy, and E. Sithirasanen	Localization of Submerged Sensors Using Radio and Acoustic Signals with Single Beacon	<p>This paper addresses challenges like multipath fading and synchronization and shows us potential approaches in acoustic signal for pinpoint sensor localization.</p>
[12], 2020	A. Paul, M. Islam, F. Rahman, A. Rahman	Explored Lambert-W function integration with Cayley-Menger determinant for mobile sensors.	<p>Proposed a hybrid method to localize mobile submerged sensors in real-time.</p>
[40], 2010	Luo, Hanjiang & Zhongwen, Guo & Dong, Wei & Hong, Feng & Yiyang, Zhao	LDB: Localization with Directional Beacons for Sparse 3D Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks.	<p>Focused on using directional beacons to enhance localization accuracy in underwater environments.</p>
[42], 2011	Zhou, Robert & Zheng, James & Cui, Jun-Hong & Shi, Zhijie & Bagtzoglou, Amvrossios	Scalable Localization with Mobility Prediction for Underwater Sensor Networks.	<p>Enhanced localization accuracy by accounting for the dynamic movement of underwater nodes.</p>
[38], 2007	Erol Kantarci, Melike & Vieira, Luiz & Gerla, Mario.	AUV-Aided Localization for Underwater Sensor Networks.	<p>Focused on improving localization accuracy in sparse networks using mobile AUVs.</p>

[39], 2006	Chandrasekhar, V.; Seah, W	An Area Localization Scheme for Underwater Sensor Networks.	Emphasized reducing communication overhead while maintaining accuracy in large-scale underwater deployments.
[43], 2008	Cheng, X.; Shu, H.; Liang, Q.; Du, D.H.-C	Silent positioning in underwater acoustic sensor networks.	requires no time synchronization and provides location privacy at underwater vehicles/sensors whose locations need to be determined.
[44], 2006	Syed, Affan & Heidemann, John.	Time Synchronization for High Latency Acoustic Networks.	Focused on improving synchronization accuracy to enhance network performance.
[3], 2006	H. Cui, J. Kong, M. Gerla, and S. Zhou	The challenges of building mobile underwater wireless networks for aquatic applications	Identified key issues such as mobility, energy efficiency, and network reliability in underwater environments.
[14], 2003	P. Duff and H. Muller	Autocalibration algorithm for ultrasonic location systems	Focused on achieving high precision in ultrasonic-based localization with minimal manual calibration.
[22], 2009	J. Guevara et al.	Auto-localization in Local Positioning Systems: a closed-form range-only solution.	This paper introduced a new closed-form solution which can determine the positions of multiple static beacon nodes, by the information of distance measurement between static beacons and mobile nodes.
[18], 2006	P. Geurts, D. Ernst, L. Wehenkel	Extremely randomized trees	This paper worked on Extremely Randomized Trees for improved decision-making in machine learning which is Random Forest enhanced prediction accuracy of tree-based learning algorithms for underwater localization.

[3], 2011	A. Bishop	Transmitter power estimation for uncooperative emitters with the Cayley-Menger determinant.	introduces a method to estimate the transmission power of uncooperative radio transmitters using the Cayley-Menger matrix. It leverages geometric constraints to provide an innovative approach for power estimation based on multiple measurements in challenging signal environments.
[16], 2006	C. Bishop	Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning	
[17], 2001	L. Breiman	Random Forests	Developed Random Forests for machine learning applications. Provided a robust method for modeling non-linear relationships in underwater sensor movement.
[19], 1997	S. Hochreiter, J. Schmidhuber	Long Short-Term Memory	This Developed Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for sequential data modeling. Revolutionized time-series prediction, aiding sensor trajectory forecasting under dynamic underwater conditions.
[21], 2015	D. P. Kingma, J. Ba	Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization	Proposed the Adam optimizer for stochastic optimization in machine learning. Enhanced the efficiency of training deep learning models for underwater sensor data.
[20], 2018	A. Rahman, V. Muthukkumarasamy	Localization of Submerged Sensors with a Single Beacon for Non-Parallel Planes State	Explored localization of submerged sensors using a single beacon in non-parallel planes. Proposed beacon configuration methods for robust localization in non-parallel planes, reducing singularity issues.
[49], 2013	S. Wang, L. Chen, H. Hu, Z. Xue, and W. Pan	Underwater Localization and Environment Mapping Using Wireless Robots	This paper integrates sensor data to enhance navigation and mapping accuracy. It proposes innovative techniques for cooperative localization and real-time environmental mapping.
[34], 2006	N. J.-H. Cui, N. J. Kong, M. Gerla, and N. S. Zhou	The challenges of building scalable mobile underwater wireless sensor	This paper focuses on issues like limited bandwidth, dynamic topology, and energy constraints. It presents potential solutions for improving

		networks for aquatic applications	scalability and reliability in aquatic applications.
[50], 2011	A. Stefanov and M. Stojanovic	Design and Performance Analysis of Underwater Acoustic Networks	This paper addresses challenges like channel variability and energy efficiency. It evaluates key protocols and network architectures for reliable communication.
[23], 2018	Q.-L. Wu, Y. Zhao, Y.-N. Zhang, S.-X. Liu, Q. Zhao, and S.-Z. Chen	Theoretical analysis of seawater depth and temperature measurement with C-type micro-structured fiber grating	This paper addresses theoretical analysis of measuring seawater depth and temperature using C-type micro-structured fiber grating. It examines the fiber's sensitivity to environmental changes.
[13], 2023	W. Huang et al.	Underwater Sound Speed Profile Construction: A Review	This paper discusses various methods for constructing sound speed profiles which are critical for accurate acoustic signal propagation. It highlights the importance of environmental factors such as temperature, salinity, and pressure on sound speed.
[27], 2000	Mackenzie et al	Speed of Sound in Sea-Water	This paper presents an empirical equation to estimate sound speed based on environmental factors such as temperature, salinity, and pressure affect sound propagation.
[9], 2012	S. Misra, S. Dash, M. Khatua, A. V. Vasilakos, and M. S. Obaidat	Jamming in underwater sensor networks: detection and mitigation	The paper addresses jamming attacks in underwater sensor networks, focusing on their detection and mitigation. It reviews various techniques to identify and counteract jamming threats, which can disrupt communication in such networks.
[25], 2005	Akyildiz, Ian & Pompili, Dario & Melodia, Tommaso	Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks: Research Challenges.	Different architectures for two-dimensional and three-dimensional underwater sensor networks are discussed

[24], 2012	E. M. Sozer, M. Stojanovic and J. G. Proakis	Underwater acoustic networks	surveys of the existing network technology and its applicability to underwater acoustic channels
[5], 2011	M. Zuba, Z. Shi, Z. Peng, and J.-H. Cui	Launching denial-of-service jamming attacks in underwater sensor networks	examines denial-of-service (DoS) jamming attacks in underwater sensor networks. It discusses how these attacks can be launched and their disruptive effects on the network's functionality.
[47], 2016	S. Patil and S. Chaudhari	DoS Attack Prevention Technique in Wireless Sensor Networks	focuses on techniques for preventing Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks in wireless sensor networks. It examines methods to detect and mitigate such attacks, improving the network's resilience and ensuring reliable communication.
[7], 2018	Yanga,Dai,Si,Wang,Wang	Challenges and Security Issues in Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks	This paper focuses on the unique difficulties of securing these networks, such as energy constraints, unreliable communication channels, and vulnerability to various attacks.
[33], 2010	Y. Cong, G. Yang, Z. Wei, and W. Zhou	Security in Underwater Sensor Network	This paper explores existing security protocols and their suitability for underwater environments, emphasizing the need for robust solutions to ensure data integrity, confidentiality, and network availability.
[48], 2020	F. Al-Obaidy, N. Razfar, P. Moeini, and F. Mohammadi	Wireless Positioning Network Location Prediction Based on Machine Learning Techniques	This paper highlights the potential of machine learning to improve accuracy and efficiency in predicting node locations within wireless networks. The study focuses on how these techniques can enhance positioning systems, particularly in environments where traditional methods face challenges.
[14], 2013	Anisur Rahman, Vallipuram Muthukkumarasamy, Elankayer Sithirasanen	The Analysis of Temperature, Depth, Salinity Effect on Acoustic Speed	The study indicates that temperature, depth, and salinity all influence the speed of sound in water. The speed normally increases with rising temperature and depth (pressure),

		for a Vertical Water Column	while decreasing with increasing salinity.
[15],	Anisur Rahman	The Effect of in-situ Underwater Acoustic Speed on Localization of Submerged Sensors	Investigate how differences in underwater speed affect the accuracy of submerged sensor localization. Sound travels at different speeds based on the water's qualities such as temperature and salinity. This variance may generate mistakes in underwater sensor localization approaches that rely on auditory inputs.

Chapter 3

Detailed Methodology

3.1. Problem Field

3.1.1 Localization of Submerged Sensor

The use of a single surface beacon for underwater sensor localization poses significant challenges in dynamic ocean environments. First, the assumption that submerged sensors remain stationary introduces limitations as ocean currents and environmental factors often cause sensor drift complicating accurate localization [20]. Second, co-linearity and co-planarity issues may arise if the single beacon moves in linear or planar trajectories relative to the submerged sensors. Such geometric constraints can lead to singularity problems in localization equations making solutions indeterminate [10,20]. Lastly, the process is highly time-consuming as a single beacon requires multiple positional changes and may need six or more to collect sufficient data for localization while necessitating complex and resource-intensive ship maneuvers. These challenges underline the need for robust multi-beacon configurations that mitigate these issues, improve efficiency, and ensure precise underwater localization.

3.1.2 Determination of Acoustic signal speed

In the proposed localization method, we said we have six beacons on the surface of the ocean column and three sensors to collect information about the marine environment are deployed underwater. And here we need distance measurement. As we know the velocity of a signal across a medium or channel cannot be considered constant and this statement is especially true for non-homogenous communication mediums like ocean. The acoustic speed throughout water has a greater impact by environmental factors like temperature, depth and salinity [15] and it has been found to be a function of these three environmental factors. The signal also does not follow a signal path to proceed [31]. Let's discuss these three natural factors in a little bit of detail,

Temperature: Generally, for most areas of the marine environment, the water temperature gradually declines from the surface to bottom but we can find different local variation there, in the shallow level we can normally observe this variation with respect to time and depth more than other places (i.e solar thermal, ocean currents, natural season variations etc.).[31]

Salinity: The dissolved salt in pure water can affect the speed of the sound. Mostly, this variation takes place near the surface where generally this environmental impact happens. The unit of salinity is particularly considered in p.p.t(parts per thousand) or in p.s.u(practical salinity units) [31].

Figure No: 3.1.2 (Sound Speed Variation with Temperature and Salinity)

Depth: Its information primarily indicated by sea water pressure which is used to accurate localization in marine environment [23]. Usually, fluid statistics impact the sound speed and increase it with respect to depth in fact temperature and salinity underwater also differ in respect of depth. If any increment of the depth is found then we will observe the decrease in temperature and increment in salinity on base of specific range [31].

Density can be considered another environmental factor but usually it is determined using the temperature and salinity. Usually, hot water is less density and cold water has high density and that's why we can find warmer water on the surface while colder water at the bottom level. Similarly, temperature and salinity also influence density. The higher salinity will have higher density and lower will have lower density and that's why saline water will be submerged underwater but pure or fresh water will hover on the surface.

In this work we can consider the sensor at any layer while it satisfies the empirical formulas parameter. To measure the acoustic speed value first we need to know the value of temperature, depth and salinity at the beacon positions and for the sensor positions. The variable values for the beacons are mostly straightforward; we can determine the temperature and salinity at zero depth but the main challenges arise for the sensor nodes if sensors are not included with the nodes [15]. In this work we will measure the velocity of sound using different suitable empirical equations and we will use Mackenzie formula to analyze the effect of these environmental factors on the speed. In this work we consider the sensors are static on the time of computation for simplicity and also, we ignore the mobility of the sensor nodes as our concentration of this work is to measure the speed of sound and examine the effect of previously mentioned variables on velocity

3.1.3 Jamming detection in Underwater Wireless Networking

UWSN has established evidence of strength over different types of application like marine monitoring, underwater materials consideration, surveillance or for military usage etc. [7].

In WSN one of the major challenges to provide network security is because of the dynamicity and the open space nature of the transmission channel, which make these networks more vulnerable for both collecting and monitoring than wired networks. And this is one of the important concerns for security in WSN. As in modern times the increment of wireless devices like IoT ecosystem creates another problem because with weak security measurement generally developed equipment with low operational power makes it an easy target for cyber breach [33].

As it is considered a variant of sensor network the characteristics of the UWSN are very similar with grounded wired networks and their security requirements are also similar [33]:

- Confidentiality: Make the information or data safe and secret from any type of malicious intrusion and the message should only be seen by sending and receiving nodes.
- Authentication: The information can easily be tampered by outsiders so nodes need to authenticate the received information source.
- Integrity: It ensures that the data or the information is not modified by any hackers.
- Availability: This makes sure that the network has robustness and is able to deliver even if the network is under attack.
- Freshness: It means the same should not be re-transmitted again and again in the network and always transmit new and fresh information on the network.

For providing this feature to our network we have to make it secure from any type of cyber-attacks. Because of the unique properties of long latency, close to the ground bandwidth and an excessive error rate underwater medium introduced a great challenge while designing a protocol [34]. There are different types of parameters to detect jamming. For this work we will consider the matrices to detect the event PSR PDR and ECA. These are some common parameters of WSN. The definition of them is

- PSR: The ratio of successfully sent packets by a legalized transport source, differentiate to the total number of packets it wanted to send to the network [8].
- PDR: It is the ratio of the successfully delivered packets to the target place compared to the total packet attempted to deliver. [8]
- ECA: It is the amount of power or energy used by a wireless device to execute a task. It is a very useful parameter as all wireless devices use batteries as power sources which is very minimal [35].

We are going to use this parameter for our desired network where we consider we have one beacon and three submerged sensors and assumed the given system

- Beacon can generate acoustic signals and radio signals.
- Communication will be affected by environmental impurities.
- All sensors include because they will have unique node IDs.

Here we will set a threshold value for each parameter and whenever the actual value crosses the threshold value we will consider it as a jamming event on the communication medium. The main target of the adversary is to increase the wastage of energy in the wireless network as it is very difficult to repair the sensors frequently in such a harsh climate as the ocean. And whenever the communication channel is jammed the sensor will simultaneously re-transmit the same data which will also increase the amount of energy usage and if this process continues our network will not be able to function. And if we use this parameter and whenever we find these types of incidents occurring, we will increase the sleep ration of the nodes and they can be saved from the extra usage of power and the battery life of the sensors will also be intact.

3.2 Placement of Beacons and Sub-Beacons

3.2.1 Positioning the surface and submerged beacons

Figure No: 3.2.1 (Positioning of surface beacons)

The proposed methodology for underwater sensor localization effectively addresses challenges specific to underwater environments by utilizing a configuration of surface beacons arranged in a pentagonal shape in Figure 3.2.1. The spatial arrangement of these beacons labeled as Point 1, Point 2, Point 3, Point 4, and Point 5 ensures a well-distributed geometric layout that eliminates the risk of co-linearity or co-planarity among the beacons. These points are strategically positioned

along the perimeter of the pentagon forming a closed loop connected by red dashed lines in the plot. This non-linear geometric arrangement plays a critical role in mitigating singularity issues commonly encountered when employing the CMD.

In this research, we investigate the localization of submerged sensors using a network of surface beacons with a particular emphasis on identifying a lost submerged sensor. Figure 3.2.2 illustrates the process of calculating the distances between six surface beacons to the deployed submerged sensors and lost sensors.

Figure No: 3.2.2 (calculation of distances between six surface beacons)

3.2.2 The Dynamics of Acoustic Signals

Acoustic signals are widely regarded as the most effective method for underwater sensor localization due to their superior propagation characteristics in aquatic environments as compared to radio signals and GPS-based systems. In UWSNs acoustic channels are naturally employed and range measurement using acoustic signals is much more accurate than using radio [36,37]. Unlike radio signals acoustic signals can travel much longer distances with minimal loss of energy and don't suffer significant attenuation and distortion in underwater environments. The primary reason for this difference is that radio waves are quickly absorbed by water particularly in deeper and turbid conditions which significantly reduces their range and reliability [38]. In contrast, acoustic waves owing to their lower attenuation in water offer a more reliable means of communication and distance measurement for underwater applications making them well-suited for localization tasks. The use of GPS-based systems for underwater localization is impractical due to the inability of GPS signals to penetrate water beyond a shallow depth. Acoustic signals do not suffer from this limitation and can successfully provide localization information to submerged sensors at various depths making them indispensable for underwater navigation systems.

Table No: 02 (comparison of GPS, Acoustic, Radio signals)

Feature	GPS (Underwater)	Acoustic	Radio (Underwater)
Effectiveness	Ineffective underwater	Highly effective underwater	Limited to short distances
Range	Requires surface relay	Up to a few kilometers	Tens of meters
Speed	Not applicable	Slow (~1500 m/s in water)	Fast (~300,000 km/s, rapid loss)
Applications	Surface navigation relay only	Underwater positioning & comms	Experimental, short-range use

The key advantage of acoustic signals for underwater localization lies in the use of multiple schemes of sensor localization. Schemes can be classified as range-free and range-based schemes. Range-free schemes localize a sensor node by deducing distance information [8,5]. Range-based distance measurements use techniques like ToA and TDoA [41,42,38]. Range-based methods generally offer more accurate positioning. Time synchronization between sensor nodes is typically required for the ToA techniques [43,41] precise time synchronization is challenging in underwater

environments [44]. In [22], Guevara et al. introduced a new closed-form solution where no position information of any nodes is required to determine the positions of multiple static beacon nodes used as the distance measurement between static beacons and mobile nodes. The distance d between a surface beacon and a submerged sensor can be calculated by the following equation:

$$d = \frac{(T_{TOA} - T_{proc})}{2} \times V_{acoustic}$$

.....(1)

Where:

- d is the distance between the surface beacon and the submerged sensor,
- T_{TOA} is the measured time of arrival of the signal,
- T_{proc} is the processing time of the submerged sensor,
- $V_{acoustic}$ is the speed of sound in water (typically between 1450 m/s and 1550 m/s, depending on water temperature, salinity, and depth).

The calculated one-way signal travel time is then multiplied by the acoustic signal speed, $V_{acoustic}$ to estimate the distance between the beacon and the submerged sensor. This method assumes that the signal travels along a straight path between the surface beacon, the submerged sensor, and that there is minimal signal distortion due to environmental factors such as turbulence or interference.

Once the distances from all six surface beacons to the submerged sensor are obtained then an optimization-based approach can be used to triangulate the exact location of the submerged sensor. This approach relies on solving a system of equations that represent the distances from each beacon to the sensor using techniques such as least-squares minimization or other forms of nonlinear optimization as described in [10] and [41]. These distances are treated as constraints and the optimization algorithm iteratively adjusts the estimated position of the submerged sensor to minimize the error between the computed and actual distances.

This localization technique is based on acoustic time-of-flight measurements and is a widely adopted method for submerged sensor networks particularly in dynamic and noisy underwater environments where traditional GPS systems are not feasible. The accuracy of the localization depends on the precision of the TOF measurements and the stability of the acoustic signal propagation speed and the geometry of the beacon arrangement [11], [12].

3.2.3 positioning the surface and submerged beacons

In the previous section, we tackled the problem of localizing submerged sensors using a geometric configuration of surface beacons arranged in a pentagonal shape. This arrangement was chosen specifically to eliminate the risk of collinearity or coplanarity which are common issues that can lead to singularities in trilateration calculations. The localization process is based on trilateration where the distances between the sensor nodes and the surface beacons are used to form a set of equations that allow for the determination of the sensors' positions in three-dimensional space.

The localization of submerged sensors in underwater environments using surface beacons involves a precise geometric approach leveraging trilateration based on known distances between the sensors and beacons. The positions of three submerged sensor nodes are labeled as S_1, S_2, S_3 are assumed to be at the origin of the coordinate system while the positions of the surface beacons S_4, S_5, \dots, S_9 are predetermined. The distances between each beacon and the submerged sensors such as $d_{14}, d_{24},$ and d_{34} are measured and these values are the inputs used in the localization algorithm. The distances between the submerged sensors themselves such as $d_{12}, d_{13},$ and d_{23} along with the volume of the tetrahedron formed by the sensors and beacons denoted as V_t are initially unknown and must be calculated.

To calculate the unknowns, we need the volume of the tetrahedron is computed using the Cayley-Menger determinant which provides a means to derive the volume of a simplex based on the squared distances between its vertices. The Cayley-Menger determinant for the tetrahedron formed by the three submerged sensors and three surface beacons is represented as follows:

$$V_t = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & d_{14}^2 & d_{24}^2 & d_{34}^2 \\ 1 & d_{14}^2 & 0 & d_{23}^2 & d_{13}^2 \\ 1 & d_{24}^2 & d_{23}^2 & 0 & d_{12}^2 \\ 1 & d_{34}^2 & d_{13}^2 & d_{12}^2 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

This determinant allows the computation of the volume V_t which is essential for calculating the distances between the sensor nodes and the beacons. Once V_t is known that a system of linear equations can be established to determine the unknown inter-sensor distances and the coordinates of the submerged sensors.

The choice of a pentagonal arrangement for the surface beacons is significant in avoiding collinearity and coplanarity which may occur singularities in the determinant and cause computational errors. By ensuring the beacons are positioned in a way that avoids these problematic configurations, the algorithm becomes more stable and less prone to failure.

This approach, relying on the Cayley-Menger determinant and strategically placed surface beacons are widely used in underwater sensor localization due to its robustness. It has been demonstrated in several studies to be effective in overcoming the unique challenges posed by underwater environments where GPS-based localization methods are not feasible due to signal attenuation and the difficulty of obtaining precise measurements. Rahman et al. [20] highlighted the usefulness of the Cayley-Menger determinant in underwater localization systems. This determinant provides a means of computing the volume of the tetrahedron which is essential for deriving the coordinates of the sensor. Once this volume is known a system of linear equations can be formulated to determine the unknown distances between the sensor nodes and the beacon. These equations can then be solved using standard linear algebra techniques such as Gaussian elimination or least-squares minimization.

3.3 Calculation

3.3.1 Linearizing the System of Equations

To solve the nonlinear system of distance equations, the problem is linearized. This is done by introducing new unknown variables X_n for each element in the distance equation. The linearized system of equations takes the general form:

$$A \cdot X = b \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where,

A = matrix containing the coefficients of the distance terms

X = vector of unknowns (the coordinates of the sensors)

b = vector of constants (the measured distances).

The linear system can be solved iteratively with each step refining the estimate of the sensor positions.

The following set of equations represents the linear system for the localization problem:

$$a_1x_1+a_2x_2+a_3x_3\dots\dots\dots a_nx_n=b \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where $a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_n$ are the coefficients derived from the distances between the beacon and the sensor nodes and b is the corresponding vector of known measurements. By solving this system, the unknown coordinates of the sensors can be estimated.

3.3.2 Distance Computation and Final Localization

Once the linear system is solved the distances between the sensor nodes, d_{12} , d_{13} , and d_{23} , can be computed using the following equations: $d_{12} = \sqrt{y^2}$, $d_{13} = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$, $d_{23} = \sqrt{(x - y)^2 + y^2}$ Where x and y represent the coordinates of the sensor nodes. For example, if the sensor nodes S_1, S_2, S_3 have coordinates (0,0,0), (0,y,0), and (x,y,0), respectively, then the distances between the sensor nodes can be expressed as:

$$d_{12} = \sqrt{y^2} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

$$d_{13} = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

$$d_{23} = \sqrt{(x - y)^2 + y^2} \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

The distances between the beacon and the sensors along with the inter-sensor distances are used to refine the position estimation of the sensors. After solving for the unknown distances, the 3D coordinates of the sensor nodes are determined with high accuracy.

3.4. ML-Driven Future Localization Dynamic Currents

3.4.1 Prediction Model

Accurate localization of submerged sensors is crucial in underwater wireless sensor networks particularly for dynamic environments influenced by ocean currents. Building on prior calculations this study achieves precise localization using a single beacon and incorporates predictive modeling to address dynamic factors. The Cayley-Menger determinant is used as a foundational approach for determining the position of submerged sensors by capturing geometric relationships among sensors and beacons. This method has been validated as effective in scenarios involving non-parallel planes as highlighted by Rahman and Muthukkumarasamy [10,20].

By taking multiple measurements of the submerged sensor (e.g., 60 iterations), machine learning models are leveraged to predict its future positions. Machine learning techniques including Linear Regression, Random Forests, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) offer robust frameworks for handling time-series data and dynamic changes in environmental conditions. Random Forests as introduced by Breiman [17], provide high accuracy for regression problems with minimal overfitting. Similarly, RNNs and their variants such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) excel in sequential data processing and have been extensively applied to oceanographic prediction tasks [19][21].

This study integrates machine learning with physical models to enhance prediction capabilities. For example, by combining machine learning with the Cayley-Menger determinant the system adapts to environmental changes such as current-induced drift which are often challenging to account for in static localization models.

To ensure the reliability of future position estimates time-series data collected from submerged sensors is processed using ensemble methods and deep learning. The utility of neural networks in underwater sensor tracking particularly in predicting drift and environmental influences. Furthermore, the use of Cayley-Menger determinants in conjunction with linearized geometric equations ensures computational efficiency and precision [11].

By combining mathematical modeling with machine learning this approach offers a comprehensive solution for dynamic underwater environments. The proposed methodology is scalable and can accommodate larger sensor networks with varying configurations making it suitable for diverse applications in oceanographic research, underwater navigation, and marine robotics.

3.5 Analysis of Acoustic speed and the effect of environmental factors

At present the use of wireless sensor networks or WSN is more popular in underwater than terrestrial environments.

As we know in underwater environments, we use acoustic signals instead of radio signals because of its properties mentioned in the TABLE No 03 [11]

Table No: 03 (PROPERTIES OF RADIO AND ACOUSTIC SIGNALS)

	Radio Signals		Acoustic Signals	
	Vacuum	Water	Vacuum	Water
Velocity	3×10^8 m/s	$\approx 2.25 \times 10^6$ m/s	≈ 1500 m/s	V_A
Range	-	1.8-323m	-	1-100km

So, from the above **TABLE No: 03** we can say the acoustic signal speed is much slower than the radio signal but it can travel more distance than the radio signal can. In our work we will consider the acoustic signal as used for communication purposes. Simple Underwater Acoustic Networks are establishing two-way transmission between various equipment underwater for real-time communication [24]. Here, for distance measurement and communicating with each other in **Figure No: 3.2.2** we use acoustic signals which does determine the distance between our surface beacons and submerged sensors. But in an underwater environment while calculating the acoustic speed we need to consider environmental factors as acoustic signals massively rely on factors like temperature, depth and salinity. To accurately localize the inter point distance among the surface beacon and sensors should be calculated precisely as much as possible [16].

In order to find the value of acoustic speed V_A we need to take the consideration of temperature, depth and the salinity of the deployed beacons and sensors position respectively [18].

In the traditional way of calculating the distance where velocity and traveled time are considered to calculate the distance [45],

$$\text{Distance (d)} = \frac{1}{2} \times \text{speed of sound (V)} \times \text{travel time (t)} \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

In equation (8) the speed of sound V is nothing but the value of acoustic signal speed V_A . We can calculate this V_A by an empirical equation applying temperature, depth and salinity information of the location and we can use different types of available equations to measure the speed of sound from simpler to most complicated ones [25].

Now let's determine the data of temperature, depth and salinity which will be used in the calculation. For our work we are going to consider the real life collected information of seven islands, two flooded rocky reefs and the Santa Catarina coast along with southern Brazil amid the location coordinates of 26°22' S and 28°26' S where we have temperature and depth from [25] which is in between range for temperature (T) 14.421°C to 29.252 °C and for depth(D) it is from 5 m to 22.1 m. and assume the salinity(S) value from 20.5 ppt to 35 ppt only for calculation purpose as we did not have the value of salinity in real time. And if the impact of this parameter has less effect on the speed of sound, then we can determine the speed value V_A accurately. The researcher has introduced different types of empirical equations to determine the acoustic speed using the information of temperature, depth and salinity of the water column. We have seven empirical equations with different coefficients and from [13,27,14]

We have,

Mackenzie empirical formula:

$$v(D,S,T) = 1448.96 + 4.591T - 5.304 \times 10^{-2}T^2 + 2.374 \times 10^{-4}T^3 + 1.340(S-35) + 1.630 \times 10^{-2}D + 1.675 \times 10^{-7}D^2 - 1.025 \times 10^{-2}T(S - 35) - 7.139 \times 10^{-13}TD^3$$

.....(9)

The range of validity for this equation is temperature 2 to 30 °C, salinity 25 to 40 parts per thousand (ppt) and depth 0 to 8000 m.

Medwin empirical formula:

$$v(D,S,T) = 1449.2 + 4.6t - 0.055t^2 + 0.00029t^3 + (1.34 - 0.01t)(S - 35) + 0.016D$$

.....(10)

where T,S,and D have the same meaning and unit with Leroy empirical formula. Medwin empirical formula can be applied over the range of temperature 0 to 35°C, salinity 0 to 45 ppt, and depth up to 1000 m.

Chen–Millero empirical formula:

$$v(\mathbf{D,S,T}) = 1449.05 + 4.57t - 0.0521t^2 + 0.00023t^3 + (1.333 - 0.0126t + 0.00009t^2)(S - 35.0) \dots\dots\dots(11)$$

For this, T which is temperature 0 to 40 °C, salinity as S 0 to 40 parts per thousand, and P is pressure 0 to 1000 bar.

Wilson empirical formula:

$$v(\mathbf{D,S,T}) = (S - 35)(-1.1244 \times 10^{-2}t + 7.7711 \times 10^{-7}t^2 + 7.7016 \times 10^{-5}p - 1.2943 \times 10^{-7}p^2 + 3.1580 \times 10^{-8}pt + 1.5790 \times 10^{-9}pt^2) + p(-1.8607 \times 10^{-4}t + 7.4812 \times 10^{-6}t^2 + 4.5283 \times 10^{-8}t^3) + p^2(-2.5294 \times 10^{-7}t + 1.8563 \times 10^{-9}t^2) + p^3(-1.9646 \times 10^{-10}t) \dots\dots\dots(12)$$

Wilson formula can be applied over the range of temperature -4°C to 30°C, salinity 0 to 37 and pressure 0 to 1000 kg/cm³

Leroy empirical formula:

$$v(\mathbf{D,S,T}) = 1.492.9 + 3(t-10) - 0.006(t-10)^2 - 0.04(t-18)^2 + 1.2(S-10) - 0.01(S-35)(T-18) + D/61 \dots\dots\dots(13)$$

Where t is the temperature in °C, S is the salinity in ppt, and D is the depth in m. Leroy empirical formula can be applied over the range of temperature from -2°C to 34°C, salinity from 20 to 42, and depth up to 8000 m.

Coppens empirical formula:

$$v(\mathbf{D,S,T}) = 1449.05 + 4.57t - 0.0521t^2 + 0.00023t^3 + (1.333 - 0.0126t + 0.00009t^2)(S - 35.0) \dots\dots\dots(14)$$

where we consider T is the temperature in °C, S is the salinity in ppt, and Z is the depth in m. Coppens empirical formula can be applied within the range of: temperature [0,35°C], salinity 0 to 45 ppt, and depth up to 4000 m

Del Grosso empirical formula:

$$v(\mathbf{D,S,T}) = -0.127562783426 \times 10^{-1}tS + 0.635191613389 \times 10^{-2}tp + 0.265484716608 \times 10^{-7}t^2p^2 - 0.159349479045 \times 10^{-5}tp^2 + 0.522116437235 \times 10^{-9}tp^3 - 0.438031096213 \times 10^{-6}t^3p - 0.161674495909 \times 10^{-8}S^2p^2 + 0.968403156410 \times 10^{-4}t^2S + 0.485639620015 \times 10^{-5}tS^2p - 0.340597039004 \times 10^{-3}tpS \dots\dots\dots(15)$$

Here, temperature T 0 to 30 °C, salinity which 30 to 40 parts per thousand(ppt) and pressure 0 to 1000 kg/cm³,

Each equation has different types of range for the three environmental parameters. Now we need to see if we can apply all these empirical equations with our range as we can see all empirical equations have their own range for all three parameters temperature, depth and salinity. To check that, we need to have the unit of the equation parameter to be the same as our parameter unit unless we cannot calculate with our desired data of the environmental parameters. As we can see in equation no: (12) and (15) of ‘Wilson’ and ‘Del-Grosso’ have the unit of depth in kg/cm³ and equation no:

(11) ‘Chen–Millero’ has the unit bar for depth.

To determine the acoustic speed using these empirical formulas first convert these units to the meter or m according to our information.

To convert the depth value into a meter we will use the following formula [27],

$$Z_s(P, \Phi) = \frac{9.72659 \times 10^2 P - 2.512 \times 10^{-1} P^2 + 2.279 \times 10^{-4} P^3 - 1.82 \times 10^{-7} P^4}{g(\Phi) + 1.092 \times 10^{-4} P} \dots\dots\dots(16)$$

Where, $g(\Phi)$ is considered the international gravity formula and it is calculated using

$$g(\Phi) = 9.780318 (1 + 5.2788 \times 10^{-3} \sin^2 \Phi + 2.36 \times 10^{-5} \sin^4 \Phi) \dots\dots\dots(17)$$

- Were,
- Z = depth in meters
- P = pressure in MPa
- Φ = latitude

so , using the information of latitude (Φ) from [26] we can take the average value of latitude given there which is 27.38502 and for the pressure P

$$\begin{aligned} P &= 1000 \text{ kg/ } kg/cm^3 = 1000000 \text{ kg/m}^3 \times 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 \\ &= 9810000/1000000 \\ &= 9.81 \text{ MPa} \end{aligned}$$

And using the equation no :(17) we have

$$\begin{aligned} g(\Phi) &= 9.780318 \text{ m/s}^2 \\ Z &= 972.97 \text{ m.} \end{aligned}$$

And if we put this and other given value in the equation no: (16) we will have

And for bar to meter, we will,

$$1 \text{ MPa} = 10 \text{ bar}$$

$$\text{So, } 1000 = 100 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\text{So, } g(\Phi) = 9.79125 \text{ m/s}^2$$

And the value of depth will become,

$$Z = 9679.8 \text{ m.}$$

So, we can say in our case we can calculate using equation no: (11) , (12) and (15) till the depth range of 972.97 m and 9679.8 m.

Now, from **TABLE No:04 [46]** So, we can see all the range of the parameter,

Table No: 04 (Empirical formula comparison)

Empirical formula Proposed year	Empirical formula Proposed year	Application range		
		temperature	depth/pressure	salinity
Mackenzie empirical formula	1981	[2°C, 30°C]	[0,8000m]	[25-40]
Medwin empirical formula	1975	[0,35°C]	[0,1000m]	[0,45]
Chen–Millero empirical formula	1977	[0, 40°C]	[0,9679.8m]	[5,40]
Wilson empirical formula	1960	[-4°C, 30°C]	[0,972.97m]	[0 - 37]
Leroy empirical formula	1969	[-2°C, 34 °C]	[0,8000 m]	[0-42]
Coppens empirical formula	1981	[0,35°C]	[0, 4000 m]	[0,45]
Del Grosso empirical formula	1974	[0 - 30°C]	[0,972.97m]	[30-40]

We can say after going through the parameter range of all empirical equations we can say we can use all of them in our case according to our chosen value of temperature, depth and salinity.

Our main objective of this part is to measure the average acoustic speed and analysis of the effect of environmental factors so we will consider ‘Mackenzie’ as our base formula to see the effect of the temperature, depth and salinity on the sound of speed but we will find average speed for each of the seven empirical equations mentioned above.

After taking measurement of temperature(T) , depth(D) and salinity(S) and communicating with beacon which is equipped with top to bottom surface values, we can calculate the average acoustic speed using the following formula[15]

$$v_{avg} = f_{avg} (T, D, S) = \frac{1}{A} \int_{S_i}^{S_f} \int_{D_i}^{D_f} \int_{T_i}^{T_f} f(T,D,S) dA \dots\dots\dots(18)$$

$$= \frac{1}{A} \int_{S_i \geq 20.5}^{S_f \leq 35} \int_{D_i \geq 5}^{D_f \leq 22.1} \int_{T_i \geq 14.421}^{T_f \leq 29.252} f_{avg} (T, D, S) dT dD dS$$

Here, A is the area created by the limits of temperature, depth and salinity. And $f_{avg} (T, D, S)$ in the function of equation no: (9) to (15)

3.6 Implementation of Underwater Jamming Detection Protocol (UWJDP)

WSN are very flexible, practical and straightforward to implement. The growth of this technology can be observed because it is inexpensive and practical [13].

WSN is much more used in underwater environments than terrestrial because of its harsh nature. UWSN becomes much more challenging to provide security because of its robust and dynamic nature. It is crucial to apply protocol or techniques to make UWSN safe for communication and data transfer from nodes to nodes or in our case we can say beacons and submerged sensors. The work from S.Misra et al. [9] proposed a protocol for identifying the jamming and also what steps should be done in these scenarios. They used the characteristics of jamming and proposed the protocol named Underwater Jamming Detection Protocol or UWJDP. It successfully detects and mitigates the jamming in submerged environments. There are various types of metrics to detect

jamming in the marine environment, among them most noteworthy are CST (Carrier Sensing Time'), PSR, PDR, SNR (Signal to Noise Ratio) , ECA ,RSS(Received Signal Strength), etc. In the proposed method authors have used PSR, PDR and ECA to detect the jamming event. The authors have divided it into three phases: Identifying nearby nodes, diagnosis of jamming and lastly mapped the jammed area. But for our work we will only identify the neighbors and detect the jamming event of the nodes, more specifically which node is jammed and how the protocol works in that situation.

Firstly, we must be sure with our network architecture, it is very important in underwater wireless networks. As the structure is deployed underwater different forms of architecture can be possible for UWSN.

We will consider a WSN for our work where we have four nodes, one is a beacon and other three are submerged sensors.

Figure No: 3.6.1 (UWSN architecture)

Basically, the beacon is floating and the three submerged sensors are deployed underwater. It is considered one of the common and simple architectures for WSN which forms a tetrahedron shape. Here the beacon can be considered the hub link of architecture. Though this is one of the basic architecture of WSN, still this type of topology has few drawbacks, one of them is if the breakdown

occurs in the hub, whole network will be shut down and also fail to cover very large areas[40], but still this type of basic architecture are useful for a particular period of time for recording necessary information and also sometime monitoring environmental constraints like salinity , temperature , oxygen level of the selected depth. In this architecture we can see four nodes are neighbors of each other. And they confirm it by throwing an acknowledgement packet which is ‘hello’ and after the other nodes acknowledge it and send a reply to it can consider that node as its adjacent. Here the broadcast message is replied by producing some acceptance signal which is helping to discover the neighbor. This stage has similarity like the phase we can see in R-MAC [47], where each node selects a time randomly and then transmits a packet which is called ‘Neighbor Discovery’ or ‘ND’ packet.

The proposed pseudocode by S.Misra et al.[9] is given in the **Figure No: 3.6.2** where we can see both mechanism for sender and also for the receiver to detect the jamming attack and this logic will be applied and run for every single node and the value of PSR is used to detect jamming from sender and PDR is used from the receive side to detect the jamming event and ECA will be used in both cases for sender and receiver. As the proposed method works very well when the PDR ratio is around 80%, we need to set a threshold value for both PSR, PDR and for ECA as PSR and PDR have a connection with ECA. As the increment on the value of PSR and PDR will also increase the value of ECA. Because when PSR and PDR value is increasing it indicates that the message is re-transmitted repeatedly and that the device is losing energy then it requires to transmit the same message recurrently. So, for that lets consider the threshold value of PDR and PSR to 0.8 in other word let's say 80% success rate of message transmission and for ECA it can be considered 60% or 0.6.

[1] Jamming Detection for Sender	[2] Jamming Detection for Receiver
<p style="text-align: center;">Algorithm 1.</p> <hr/> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Procedure JammingDetectionSender(PSR,ECA) 2. Begin 3. If PSR < PSR_{th} and ECA > ECA_{th} //indicate jamming 4. SendEmergencyPacket() 5. Increase Sleep-Wake ratio 6. Else if PSR < PSR_{th} and ECA < ECA_{th} //indicate channel busy 7. Wait() 8. Else if PSR > PSR_{th} and ECA > ECA_{th} //indicate congestion 9. BetterRoutingRoutes() 10. Else //indicate normal scenario 11. Normal Service() 12. Endif 13. End <hr/>	<p style="text-align: center;">Algorithm 2.</p> <hr/> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Procedure JammingDetectionReceiver(PDR,ECA) 2. Begin 3. If PDR < PDR_{th} and ECA > ECA_{th} //indicate jamming 4. SendEmergencyPacket () 5. Increase Sleep-Wake Ratio 6. Else if PDR < PDR_{th} and ECA < ECA_{th} //indicate poor channel 7. Wait () 8. Else if PDR > PDR_{th} and ECA > ECA_{th} //indicate bad route 9. BetterRoutingRoutes() 10. Else //indicate normal scenario 11. Send periodic acknowledgement to the sender 12. End if 13. End <hr/>

Figure No: 3.6.2 (Pseudocode for UWJDP for Sender & Receiver)

From the above figure we can see when the node detects the value of PSR is decreased then PSR_{th} and ECA has increased than ECA_{th} it indicates jamming and sends a emergency packet by using **SendEmergencyPacket()** function but if the value of ECA does not cross the value of ECA_{th} then we will consider that the media is busy and the node will wait to transmit again when the channel is idle. It will to similar from the receiver end where it will measure the difference of PDR and PDR_{th} value. And similarly, when it finds that PDR is lower than PDR_{th} and ECA is higher than ECA_{th} it will sense it as jammed and send an emergency packet to its neighbor by applying the **SendEmergencyPacket ()** function.

And there will be a table which will contain all the information of the procedure which is detecting the jamming event among all four nodes.

Table N0: 05(High priority packet format)

Location	Node_ID	Timestamp	ACK	Jammed Bit (0/1)

The information of the jamming detection of the nodes will be stored in the formation of a time similar to **Table No:05** where we will have four information which are location (coordinates of the sensors and beacon), Node_ID(e.g. For a submerged sensor node id is 1) , Timestamp(when does the event occur), ACK indicated the acknowledgement packet number saved in numerical which indicates the number of emergency packet send by a node and lastly the Jammed Bit(0/1) where 0 indicates not jammed and 1 means jammed.

Chapter 4

Experimental Results and Analysis

4.1 localization result

The simulation to determine the coordinates of submerged sensors in a 3-D space is designed to replicate real-world scenarios of sensor localization. There are three fixed sensors positioned at specific coordinates: Sensor S1 at $[0, 0, 0]$, Sensor S2 at $[0, 60, 0]$, and Sensor S3 at $[85, 95, 0]$. A set of six surface beacons is deployed in each iteration with Beacon A1 located at a randomly generated position within the range of -20 to 20 for both x and y coordinates and at a fixed height of 50 units serving as the center of the pentagon-shaped configuration and classified as the main ship. The remaining five beacons (A2 to A6) are positioned relative to A1 forming a pentagonal arrangement in the x - y plane with each beacon placed at a consistent elevation of 50 units above the ground. Beacon A2 is placed at $[x + 30.9, y + 95.1, 50]$, Beacon A3 at $[x - 80.9, y + 58.7, 50]$, Beacon A4 at $[x - 80.9, y - 58.7, 50]$, Beacon A5 at $[x + 30.9, y - 95.1, 50]$, and Beacon A6 at $[x + 100, y, 50]$. These five beacons are considered sub-beacons deployed from the main ship (A1) then the Euclidean distance between each beacon and the three sensors is calculated to simulate real-world distance measurements. To account for potential measurement inaccuracies Gaussian noise is added to each distance. This process is repeated for 100 iterations to generate a comprehensive dataset.

The next process begins by loading the noisy distance measurements data for 100 iterations. After filtering the relevant distances for each iteration the Cayley-Menger determinant is used to calculate unknown inner distances which are essential for determining the relative positions of the sensors. Specifically, the unknown distances—denoted as d_{12} , d_{13} , and d_{23} represent the distances between the pairs of submerged sensors (S1, S2), (S1, S3), and (S2, S3), respectively. These are computed by solving a linear system of equations derived from the Cayley-Menger determinant which models the relationship between the measured distances. Once these unknown distances are calculated, the final 3-D coordinates of the sensors are determined using geometric equations. The value of the unknown coordinate of sensors is calculated. These calculated coordinates represent the final positions of the submerged sensors S1, S2, and S3.

Figure 4.1.1-4.1.3 illustrates the distance error between three submerged sensors over one hundred iterations. Notably, the maximum distance error observed occurs between sensors S1 and S3, measuring 0.5 units. For the majority of the iterations, however, the distance error is significantly smaller, with an average error of approximately 0.1 units. This minimal error demonstrates the high accuracy and reliability of the model. We can confidently conclude that this model performs exceptionally well and can serve as a dependable tool for locating lost submerged sensors.

Figure No: 4.1.1 (Distance error between S1 and S2)

Figure No: 4.1.2 (Distance error between S1 and S3)

Figure No: 4.1.3(Distance error between S2 and S3)

Figure No: 4.1.4(S2 mean error)

Figure No: 4.1.5 (S3 mean error)

Figures 4.1.4 and 4.1.5 illustrate the distance errors for sensors S3 and S2, respectively, over one hundred iterations. For Figure Y, representing sensor S3, the mean error is 0.17 units, indicating slightly larger fluctuations in accuracy. In contrast, Figure YY, representing sensor S2, shows a mean error of 0.11 units, highlighting a more precise performance. Despite these variations, both errors remain minimal, showcasing the model's overall robustness and reliability in estimating distances between submerged sensors.

4.2 Predicting Future Positions with Machine Learning

We simulated the movement of a lost sensor due to ocean currents. A random function was employed To generate values representing the ocean current's influence on the sensor's displacement within a defined x,y plane. The sensor's position was updated in each iteration, with this process repeated 60 times to capture the variability of the sensor's movement over time. For each iteration, the Euclidean distance between successive sensor positions was calculated and Gaussian error was added to simulate the inaccuracies commonly encountered in real-world data collection processes. This error was introduced to reflect typical sensor noise and measurement imprecision, which is crucial for the robustness of the predictive models. Subsequently, the Cayley-Menger determinant was applied to calculate the sensor's position at each of the 60 intervals. After obtaining the sensor positions for the 60 intervals we trained multiple machine learning models to predict the future positions of the lost sensor. The models considered both the historical trajectory and the added errors in the data. Specifically, we implemented linear regression, random forest, and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) to forecast the sensor's future positions based on the previously observed movements. Each model was trained using the data from the 60 intervals. Let's analyze the predictions of future positions using different machine learning models:

No: 06(predictions of future positions using different machine learning models)

Iteration	Linear Regression		Random Forest		Recurrent Neural Networks	
	Predicted_S3_x	Predicted_S3_y	Predicted_S3_x	Predicted_S3_y	Predicted_S3_x	Predicted_S3_y
61	109.365613	122.72001	106.953538	121.491318	93.111053	103.218674
62	109.766583	123.181431	106.953538	121.491318	93.137367	103.32708
63	110.167553	123.642853	106.953538	121.491318	93.655174	103.65081
64	110.568522	124.104274	106.953538	121.491318	93.921967	103.831497
65	110.969492	124.56569	106.95353	121.491318	94.172096	104.0554

		6	8			43
66	111.370461	125.02711 7	106.95353 8	121.491318	94.389969	104.2626 65
67	111.771431	125.48853 9	106.95353 8	121.491318	94.701561	104.4799 19
68	112.1724	125.94996	106.95353 8	121.491318	95.068062	104.7156 68
69	112.57337	126.41138 2	106.95353 8	121.491318	95.420715	104.9425 89
70	112.974339	126.87280 3	106.95353 8	121.491318	95.801453	105.1772 54
71	113.375309	127.33422 5	106.95353 8	121.491318	96.217865	105.4199 14
72	113.776278	127.79564 6	106.95353 8	121.491318	96.683868	105.6746 06
73	114.177248	128.25706 8	106.95353 8	121.491318	97.196838	105.9400 1
74	114.578218	128.71849	106.95353 8	121.491318	97.754128	106.2155 91
75	114.979187	129.17991 1	106.95353 8	121.491318	98.375107	106.5059 28
76	115.380157	129.64133 3	106.95353 8	121.491318	99.07177	106.8159 03
77	115.781126	130.10275 4	106.95353 8	121.491318	99.861343	107.1622 01
78	116.182096	130.56417 6	106.95353 8	121.491318	100.765038	107.5525 36
79	116.583065	131.02559 7	106.95353 8	121.491318	101.813843	107.9797 9
80	116.984035	131.48701 9	106.95353 8	121.491318	103.053741	108.4517 67

The table presents predictions of the future positions of the lost sensor across 20 iterations using Linear Regression, Random Forest, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). Linear Regression shows a consistent and reliable performance, with predictions for x and y coordinates following a clear linear trend, making it suitable for simple continuous patterns. Random Forest performs well in the first iteration but fails to adapt over subsequent iterations, producing identical values for both x and y coordinates, indicating its limitation in handling sequential or temporal data. In contrast, RNNs excel in capturing temporal dependencies, as evident from their progressively accurate predictions over iterations, dynamically adapting to changes in x and y coordinates. These results underscore the importance of selecting models like RNNs for tasks involving sequential data, while simpler models like Linear Regression suffice for less complex patterns.

Linear Regression

Linear Regression MSE for S3_x:
1.550161407902013
Linear Regression MSE for S3_y:
3.9619723362917267
Linear Regression MAE for S3_x:
0.9978410563108646
Linear Regression MAE for S3_y:
1.5490609928485373
Linear Regression R² for S3_x: 0.98
Linear Regression R² for S3_y: 0.96
Linear Regression Accuracy: 93.63%

Figure: 4.2.1 (Linear Regression)

Random Forest

Random Forest MSE for S3_x:
2.0653192636925963
Random Forest MSE for S3_y:
5.898981018874267
Random Forest MAE for S3_x:
1.112221284962562
Random Forest MAE for S3_y:
2.062574748344956
Random Forest R² for S3_x: 0.97
Random Forest R² for S3_y: 0.94
Random Forest Accuracy: 90.92%

Fig:4.2.2 (Random Forest)

Recurrent Neural Networks

Figure: 4.2.3 (RNN accuracy on x and y axis)

RNN MSE for S3_x: 3.7648746673226525
RNN MSE for S3_y: 3.2694436419214714
RNN R² for S3_x: 0.90
RNN R² for S3_y: 0.94
RNN Accuracy: 84.47%

Figure: 4.2.4 (RNN)

4.3 Analysis of environmental factors

4.3.1 Analysis of environmental factors using Mackenzie Equation

We simulate our proposed method to determine the area of the average acoustic signal speed which was described in chapter 3.x and here we perform and verify the method. The experiment was designed based on a 3-D plot. We simulate using python programming language. In our work we have considered two environmental factors and each of them are considered as an axis and acoustic speed is considered as the third axis. Generally, the effect of salinity is not that much more than other factors, and, in our case, we did not have salinity value for our location. So, for calculation purposes we have assumed a standard value of salinity in ppt. But for the acoustic profiling we only considered the temperature and depth of our location. And, it is a fact that there has been a nearly proper result of speed in 3D plot by considering the salinity as constant.

In python,

- X-axis considered as Temperature
- Y-axis considered as Depth

- Z- axis considered as Acoustic speed

When salinity is considered as constant, the speed of acoustic with respect to depth and temperature of our simulation result is shown below,

Figure No: 4.3.1.1 (Acoustic speed profile according to Mackenzie equation)

To analyze the effect of temperature, depth and salinity we have simulated other aspects to verify which factor has the most effect on the acoustic signal. We also used python programming language for simulation purposes. We used the Mackenzie equation to calculate the average speed of sound where we considered the temperature from 14.21°C to 25.52°C, depth range was considered from 5 meter to 22.1 meter. And we assume a fixed value of 35 ppt of salinity for the calculation. We also added gaussian noise to average speed to observe variability. The value of mean we considered 0 and standard deviation of 0.3. After 100 iterations we found the mean average speed of sound is 1526.38 m/s.

Figure No: 4.3.1.2 (Average speed variation due to additive Gaussian noise)

Here, the X-axis represents the iteration number and Y-axis we put the average speed. And we also calculated the average speed with noise for each iteration. In the figure below the effect of temperature on acoustic signals is portrayed. Where it is illustrated for various surface and bottom temperatures. We computed the average speed over a depth of 5 meters to 22.1 meters using the Mackenzie equation with surface temperatures fixed at 23°C and 29°C.

Figure No: 4.3.1.3 (Average speed variation due to temperature change)

As we can see the bottom temperature increases from 2°C to 30°C, the value of the average speed also rises significantly, showing a noticeable change according to the rise of the surface temperature. We have considered the surface temperature of 23°C and 29°C and the bottom temperature from 2°C to 30°C increment. For 23°C temperature the average speed increases approximately 2 m/s and for each 5°C. It becomes more prominent when the surface temperature is higher to 29°C which is around 2.1 m/s to 2.2 m/s. So, after the relationship between bottom temperature and average sound speed for the given surface temperatures, we can say temperature variations on sound speed show us the sensitivity of sound propagation in water to thermal gradients.

In our result we will see the relationship between average sound speed and bottom temperature for varying depth ranges from 5 to 22.1 meters. The plotted graph is shown below

Figure No: 4.3.1.4 (Average speed variation due to depth change)

Here we can see only 0.2 m/s increase with each degree Celsius rise in the temperature. At a constant temperature, the sound will only increase to 0.09 m/s as the depth increases from 5 meters to 22.1 meters. As a result, if there is a 5% error on the depth measurement, we will see a negligible change in the average speed of 0.00031%. This emphasizes that while temperature significantly impacts sound speed, variations in depth from 5 to 22.1 meters have minimal effect. Here, we will illustrate the effect of salinity on the average speed of sound over a specified depth from 5 meter

to 22.1 meters, where we consider a constant surface temperature of 20°C, as salinity increases from 34.00 ppt to 34.75 ppt and therefore we can observe a gradual increase in the average speed.

Figure No: 4.3.1.5 (Average speed variation due to salinity change)

When the salinity increases by 0.25 ppt there is also a rise in the average speed which is around 0.28 m/s. Over the full increment range of 0.75 ppt the average speed of sound increases to 0.029%. Its effect is less than temperature. So, after analyzing all three-environmental factors we can come to the conclusion that temperature has the most effect than any other environment factor over average acoustic sound speed.

4.3.2 Acoustic speed measurement using different empirical equations

In this section we will see the other empirical equation,

- Medwin
- Chen-Millero
- Wilson
- Leroy
- Coppens
- Del Grosso

With the help of this equation, we can also find the average speed of acoustic signals. In the **chapter- 4.3.1** we have find the acoustic speed using Mackenzie equation and, in the figure, no: xx we have seen the 3D plot of the Makenzie equation now in this section we will see the difference

between Mackenzie with the other equation, basically we will see the difference by plotting them in 3D surface

Were,

- X- axis temperature
- Y-axis depth
- Z- axis speed

Figure No: 4.3.2.1 (Difference of Mackenzie - Medwin)

Figure No: 4.3.2.2 (Difference of Mckenzie – Chen-Millero)

Figure No: 4.3.2.3 (Difference of Mackenzie-Wilson)

Figure No: 4.3.2.4 (Difference of Mackenzie-Leroy)

Figure No: 4.3.2.5 (Difference of Mackenzie-Coppens)

Figure No: 4.3.2.6 (Difference of Mackenzie-Del Grosso)

From the six 3D surface plots which compare the sound of speed differences between Mackenzie with other six empirical equations (hen-Millero, Wilson, Leroy, Del Grosso, Medwin, and Coppens) for different temperature and depth and, we have a clear view of the difference between empirical equations.

Every empirical equation has its own uniqueness in the formula and because of that we will find different values of speed of sound for different equations. The graph below shows the average value of each graph where X-axis has the formula name, and Y-axis has the average speed.

Figure No: 4.3.2.7 (Difference speed of sound for different empirical equation)

Form the **Figure No: 4.3.2.7** we can see for each empirical equation we have the value of speed of sound which are,

- Chen-Millero equation average acoustic signal speed is 1507.45 m/s
- Leroy equation average acoustic signal speed is 1524.0.8 m/s
- Medwin equation average acoustic signal speed is 1526.30 m/s
- Mackenzie equation average acoustic signal speed is 1526.36 m/s
- Wilson equation average acoustic signal speed is 1526.45 m/s
- Del Grosso equation average acoustic signal speed is 1526.64 m/s
- Coppens equation average acoustic signal speed is 1529.46 m/s

So, we can say the value of acoustic signal is around 1507- 1529 m/s where we can find Chen-Millero has the lowest velocity of 1507.45 m/s and Coppens has the highest velocity of 1529.46 m/s. And we can say these empirical equations have something in common which are

- Formulas are sensitive to temperature and depth changes
- Coefficient Scaling
- Gaussian noise effect

Here we considered the gaussian noise mean(μ) which is equal to 0 and the σ (Standard Deviation) of 0.3. The higher the deviation we can observed more variation on the speed value.

These are some assumptions which can impact the formula to generate the low or high acoustic signal speed.

4.3.3 Underwater Jamming Detection Protocol (UWJDP)

In this part we will see how the UWJDP protocol is applied, for our work we have considered that sensor 1 is jammed as in our network architecture we have one beacon and three submerged sensors and we have drawn a 3D plot to show our network architecture and below that is shown,

For the simulation we have used python programming language.

Figure No: 4.3.3.1 (Network architecture: red circle indicating jam node and blue indicating working nodes)

So, as I mentioned we assumed that sensor 1 is jammed and another sensor is working now we will see how the UWJDP is applied

```

Node 1 sends an emergency packet: {'node_id': 1, 'location': (0, 0, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2614565, 'jammed_bit': 1}
Node 1 increases sleep-wake ratio!
Node 1: PDR is 0.5504214925731397, which is <= 0.8. Increased jamming detection probability.
Node 1 sends a hello packet: {'node_id': 1, 'location': (0, 0, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2616987, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 2 received a hello packet from Node 1: {'node_id': 1, 'location': (0, 0, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2616987, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 2 sends an acknowledgement to Node 1.
Node 3 received a hello packet from Node 1: {'node_id': 1, 'location': (0, 0, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2616987, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 3 sends an acknowledgement to Node 1.
Node 4 received a hello packet from Node 1: {'node_id': 1, 'location': (0, 0, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2616987, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 4 sends an acknowledgement to Node 1.
Node 2 sends a hello packet: {'node_id': 2, 'location': (1, 1, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2619545, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 1 received a hello packet from Node 2: {'node_id': 2, 'location': (1, 1, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2619545, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 1 sends an acknowledgement to Node 2.
Node 3 received a hello packet from Node 2: {'node_id': 2, 'location': (1, 1, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2619545, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 3 sends an acknowledgement to Node 2.
Node 4 received a hello packet from Node 2: {'node_id': 2, 'location': (1, 1, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2619545, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 4 sends an acknowledgement to Node 2.
Node 3 sends a hello packet: {'node_id': 3, 'location': (-1, -1, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2621822, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 1 received a hello packet from Node 3: {'node_id': 3, 'location': (-1, -1, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2621822, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 1 sends an acknowledgement to Node 3.
Node 2 received a hello packet from Node 3: {'node_id': 3, 'location': (-1, -1, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2621822, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 2 sends an acknowledgement to Node 3.
Node 4 received a hello packet from Node 3: {'node_id': 3, 'location': (-1, -1, -10), 'timestamp': 1722200421.2621822, 'jammed_bit': 0}
Node 4 sends an acknowledgement to Node 3.
Updating current list...
Checking current jamming status...
Forwarding list to neighbours...
Adding own entry and timestamp...

```

Figure No: 4.3.3.2 (Node Communication with Jamming Detection and Acknowledgement)

When 'Node 1' or 'Sensor 1' find itself jammed as we mentioned earlier we consider sensor 1 is already jammed and we are not using any type of hardware to simulate and that's why we are assuming it. So, when it senses jamming it updates the jamming bit attributes from the table of high priority format and increases its sleep ratio and sends emergency packets to its adjacent nodes.

And every node after getting the emergency packet from node 1 increases its sleep ratio so that it can save energy.

Node ID	Location	Timestamp	ACK	Jammed Bit
1	(0, 0, -10)	1722200421.2614565		1
1		1722200421.2615967		
1	(0, 0, -10)	1722200421.2616987		0
1	(0, 0, -10)	1722200421.2620077	2	
2	(1, 1, -10)	1722200421.2619545		0
1	(0, 0, -10)	1722200421.2622597	3	
3	(-1, -1, -10)	1722200421.2621822		0
2	(1, 1, -10)	1722200421.2617676	1	
1	(0, 0, -10)	1722200421.2616987		0
2	(1, 1, -10)	1722200421.2619545		0
2	(1, 1, -10)	1722200421.262315	3	
3	(-1, -1, -10)	1722200421.2621822		0
3	(-1, -1, -10)	1722200421.261819	1	
1	(0, 0, -10)	1722200421.2616987		0
3	(-1, -1, -10)	1722200421.2620583	2	
2	(1, 1, -10)	1722200421.2619545		0
3	(-1, -1, -10)	1722200421.2621822		0
4	(0, 0, 0)	1722200421.2618694	1	
1	(0, 0, -10)	1722200421.2616987		0
4	(0, 0, 0)	1722200421.2621067	2	
2	(1, 1, -10)	1722200421.2619545		0
4	(0, 0, 0)	1722200421.2623644	3	
3	(-1, -1, -10)	1722200421.2621822		0

Figure No: 4.3.3.3 (Packet Transmission and Jamming Detection Log)

The code of the simulation in our case revolves around a node class representing sensors and become. Here these nodes communicate to each other with the help of acknowledgement packet which can also be said “hello packet” which help them to detect jamming based on

- Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR)
- Packet Send Ratio (PSR),
- Energy Consumption Analysis (ECA)

As for simulation purposes we considered that ‘Sensor 1’ is jammed that’s why we can see in **Figure No: 4.3.3.3** that in the detection log it is 1 on the ‘Jamming Bit’ attribute.

In simple terms, when the PDR ratio is higher than the threshold value is set to 0.8, PSR threshold is set to 0.7 and the value of threshold set for ECA is 0.85. We used this threshold value to control and detect logic for our convenient network architecture. Our network becomes beneficial because

of these different values as we use different threshold values as this enhances sensitivity, reliability, and adaptability to the network monitoring and to the detection mechanism.

So, we have successfully implemented the jamming detection algorithm for UWSN and it works perfectly and with the help of the log system we get all the necessary information of the network as the attributes shown in the figure are the information of the network. With that information we can understand if a node is jammed or not and its location from its coordinates.

Chapter 5

5.1 Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated a novel method for underwater sensor localization using a pentagonal configuration of six surface beacons and the Cayley-Menger determinant. This approach proved effective in mitigating singularity issues, ensuring robust and accurate localization, and enabling rapid distance measurements. Unlike previous studies that assumed static conditions, our method allows for simultaneous distance calculations, facilitating the use of machine learning for accurate future position predictions. Additionally, the analysis of environmental factors revealed that temperature has the most significant impact on average acoustic sound speed and different empirical equations provide different acoustic speed according to their coefficient which is in between 1507 to 1526. Lastly, the successful implementation of the jamming detection algorithm, supported by a detailed logging system, provides reliable insights into network status, enabling efficient identification of jammed nodes and enhancing overall system reliability. These results collectively highlight the advancements achieved in underwater sensor localization and network robustness.

5.2 Future work:

Future research will focus on deploying the proposed localization system in real-world scenarios to validate its performance under practical environmental conditions. This includes testing in diverse underwater environments with varying temperature gradients, salinity levels, and acoustic interference to assess the system's robustness and adaptability.

Additionally, further exploration into optimizing the pentagonal beacon configuration could enhance localization accuracy and efficiency. Investigating dynamic configurations or adaptive algorithms that adjust to environmental changes in real time may provide greater flexibility and precision.

Integration with advanced machine learning models also presents a promising avenue for development. By leveraging real-world data, these models can improve predictive capabilities for sensor movement and enable adaptive decision-making in dynamic underwater conditions.

We can take the full depth range of the underwater layers (Surface Layer, Thermocline Layer, Deep Layer) to see how much the velocity increases and as for this work we see the impact of temperature on the Mackenzie equation but in future we can simulate it for all the equation and see how much the effect occurs and the difference among them.

Another potential direction is the enhancement of the jamming detection algorithm where we did not actually use any sensors or hardware to see the protocol, we just assumed a jammed node saw the workflow of the protocol but future work could focus on developing proactive countermeasures that not only identify but also mitigate the effects of jamming in real time, ensuring uninterrupted communication and localization.

Finally, expanding the scope of the system to support multi-sensor networks and enabling cooperation between multiple underwater nodes could significantly improve scalability and operational efficiency, paving the way for broader applications such as underwater exploration, environmental monitoring, and defense operations.

References:

1. S. W. Rienstra and A. Hirschberg, *An Introduction to Acoustics*, 2004.
2. M. Stojanovic, J. Catipovic, and J. G. Proakis, "Adaptive multichannel combining and equalization for underwater acoustic communications," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 94, no. 3, pp. 1621–1631, 1993.
3. C. Knowlton, "The first studies of underwater acoustics: The 1800s," *Discovery of Sound in the Sea*, May 31, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://dosits.org/people-and-sound/history-of-underwater-acoustics/the-first-studies-of-underwater-acoustics-the-1800s/>. [Accessed: Feb. 16, 2025]
4. M. Stojanovic, "Frequency reuse underwater: Capacity of an acoustic cellular network," in *Proc. 2nd Workshop Underwater Netw.*, 2007,
5. M. Zuba, Z. Shi, Z. Peng, and J.-H. Cui, "Launching denial-of-service jamming attacks in underwater sensor networks," *WUWNet '11: Proceedings of the 6th International Workshop on Underwater Networks*, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1145/2076569.2076581.
6. Y. Li, Y. Liu, Y. Wang, Z. Guo, H. Yin, and H. Teng, "Synergetic denial-of-service attacks and defense in underwater named data networking," in *IEEE INFOCOM 2020 - IEEE Conf. Comput. Commun.*, Toronto, ON, Canada, 2020, pp. 1569–1578, doi: 10.1109/INFOCOM41043.2020.9155371.
7. Yanga, Dai, Si, Wang, Wang, "Challenges and Security Issues in Underwater Wireless Sensor Networks," *International Conference on Identification, Information and Knowledge in the Internet of Things*, pp. 211–216, 2018.
8. W. Xu, W. Trappe, Y. Zhang, and T. Wood, "The feasibility of launching and detecting jamming attacks in wireless networks," in *Proc. 6th ACM Int. Symp. Mobile Ad Hoc Netw. Comput. (MobiHoc)*, 2005, pp.
9. S. Misra, S. Dash, M. Khatua, A. V. Vasilakos, and M. S. Obaidat, "Jamming in underwater sensor networks: detection and mitigation," *IET Communications*, vol. 6, no. 14, p. 2178, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1049/iet-com.2011.0641.
10. A. Rahman, "Non-Parallelism and Cayley-Menger Determinant in Submerged Localization," *Advances in Science Technology and Engineering Systems Journal*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 150–157, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.25046/aj050320.
11. A. Rahman, V. Muthukkumarasamy, and E. Sithirasenan, "Coordinates Determination of Submerged Sensors Using Cayley-Menger Determinant," *International Conference on Distributed Computing in Sensor Systems*, pp. 466–471, Jul. 2013, doi: 10.1109/dcoss.2013.62.
12. A. Paul, M. Islam, M. Rahman and A. Rahman, "Localization of Mobile Submerged Sensors using Lambert-W Function and Cayley-Menger Determinant", *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)*, Vol. 11 No. 2, 2019 DOI: 10.14569/IJACSA.2020.0110266

13. W. Huang et al., "Underwater Sound Speed Profile Construction: A Review," arXiv.org, Oct. 12, 2023. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.08251>
14. K. V. Mackenzie, "Nine term equation for sound speed in the oceans," *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 70, p. 807, 1981.
15. A. Rahman, V. Muthukkumarasamy and E. Sithirasenan, "The Analysis of Temperature, Depth, Salinity Effect on Acoustic Speed for a Vertical Water Column," 2013 IEEE International Conference on Distributed Computing in Sensor Systems, Cambridge, MA, USA, 2013, pp. 310-312, doi: 10.1109/DCOSS.2013.63.
16. C. Bishop, *Pattern Recognition and Machine Learning*, Springer, 2006.
17. Breiman, L. *Random Forests*. *Machine Learning* 45, 5–32 (2001). doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324.
18. P. Geurts, D. Ernst, and L. Wehenkel, "Extremely randomized trees," *Mach. Learn.*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 3–42, 2006, doi: 10.1007/s10994-006-6226-1.
19. S. Hochreiter and J. Schmidhuber, "Long Short-Term Memory," *Neural Computation*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1735–1780, 1997.
20. A. Rahman and V. Muthukkumarasamy, "Localization of Submerged Sensors with a Single Beacon for Non-Parallel Planes State," 2018 Tenth International Conference on Ubiquitous and Future Networks (ICUFN), Prague, Czech Republic, 2018, pp. 525-530, doi: 10.1109/ICUFN.2018.8437041.
21. D. P. Kingma and J. Ba, "Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization," *Proc. Int. Conf. Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2015.
22. J. Guevara, A. Jiménez, J. Prieto, and F. Seco, "Auto-localization algorithm for local positioning systems," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 10, pp. 1090-1100, 2012. DOI: 10.1016/j.adhoc.2012.02.003.
23. Q.-L. Wu, Y. Zhao, Y.-N. Zhang, S.-X. Liu, Q. Zhao, and S.-Z. Chen, "Theoretical analysis of seawater depth and temperature measurement with C-type micro-structured fiber grating," *Optical Fiber Technology*, vol. 47, pp. 133–140, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.yofte.2018.11.012.
24. E. M. Sozer, M. Stojanovic and J. G. Proakis, "Underwater acoustic networks," in *IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 72-83, Jan. 2000, doi: 10.1109/48.820738.
25. E. Faria-Junior and L. Alberto, "An underwater temperature dataset from coastal islands in Santa Catarina, southern Brazil: high accuracy data from different depths," *SEANOE*, Aug. 12, 2019. DOI: 10.17882/62120.
26. A. Rahman, "The effect of in-situ underwater acoustic speed on localization of submerged sensors," *Proceeding of IEEE International Symposium on a World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks 2014*, Sydney, NSW, Australia, 2014, pp. 1-2, doi: 10.1109/WoWMoM.2014.6918936.

27. "Technical Guides - Speed of sound in sea water - Underlying Physics," Npl.co.uk. [Online]. Available: <http://resource.npl.co.uk/acoustics/techguides/soundseawater/underlying-physics.html>. [Accessed: 09-Feb-2025].
28. S. Patil and S. Chaudhari, "DoS attack prevention technique in wireless sensor networks," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 79, pp. 715–721, 2016.
29. J. G. Proakis, E. M. Sozer, J. A. Rice and M. Stojanovic, "Shallow water acoustic networks," in *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 39, no. 11, pp. 114-119, Nov. 2001, doi: 10.1109/35.965368.
30. Xie, P., Cui, J.H.: 'R-MAC: An energy-efficient MAC protocol for underwater sensor networks'. *Proc. Int. Conf. on Wireless Algorithms, Systems and Applications*, IL, Chicago, 2007, pp. 187– 198.
31. X. Lurton, *An Introduction to Underwater Acoustics: Principles and Applications*, Springer Science & Business Media, Berlin, Germany, 2002.
32. M. Alabi, "Security Challenges and Solutions in Wireless Networks: A Computer Science Perspective," 2024.
33. Y. Cong, G. Yang, Z. Wei, and W. Zhou, "Security in Underwater Sensor Network," *International Conference on Communications and Mobile Computing*, pp. 162–168, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1109/cmc.2010.18.
34. N. J.-H. Cui, N. J. Kong, M. Gerla, and N. S. Zhou, "The challenges of building scalable mobile underwater wireless sensor networks for aquatic applications," *IEEE Network*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 12–18, May 2006, doi: 10.1109/mnet.2006.1637927.
35. A. Bhattacharya and P. De, "A survey of adaptation techniques in computation offloading," *J. Netw. Comput. Appl.*, vol. 78, pp. 97–115, 2017.
36. J. H. Cui, J. Kong, M. Gerla, and S. Zhou, "The challenges of building mobile underwater wireless networks for aquatic applications," *Network, IEEE*, vol. 20, pp. 12-18, 2006.
37. P. Duff and H. Muller, "Autocalibration algorithm for ultrasonic location systems," in *Seventh IEEE International Symposium on Wearable Computers*, 2003. *Proceedings*, pp. 62-68, 2003
38. Erol Kantarci, Melike & Vieira, Luiz & Gerla, Mario. (2007). *AUV-Aided Localization for Underwater Sensor Networks*. 44 - 54. 10.1109/WASA.2007.34.
39. Chandrasekhar, V.; Seah, W. *An Area Localization Scheme for Underwater Sensor Networks*. *Proceedings of the IEEE OCEANS Asia Pacific Conference*, Sydney, Australia, 16–19 May 2006; pp. 1–8.
40. Luo, Hanjiang & Zhongwen, Guo & Dong, Wei & Hong, Feng & Yiyang, Zhao. (2010). *LDB: Localization with Directional Beacons for Sparse 3D Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks*. *Journal of Networks*. 5. 10.4304/jnw.5.1.28-38.
41. H.-P. Tan, R. Diamant, W. K. G. Seah, and M. Waldmeyer, "A survey of techniques and challenges in underwater localization," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 38, no. 14–15, pp. 1663–1676, Sep. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.oceaneng.2011.07.017.

42. Zhou, Robert & Zheng, James & Cui, Jun-Hong & Shi, Zhijie & Bagtzoglou, Amvrossios. (2011). Scalable Localization with Mobility Prediction for Underwater Sensor Networks. *IEEE Trans. Mob. Comput.* 10. 335-348. 10.1109/TMC.2010.158.
43. Cheng, X.; Shu, H.; Liang, Q.; Du, D.H.-C. Silent positioning in underwater acoustic sensor networks. *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.* 2008, 57, 1756–1766.
44. Syed, Affan & Heidemann, John. (2006). Time Synchronization for High Latency Acoustic Networks. 25th IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications. 10.1109/INFOCOM.2006.161.
45. K. Hj. Talib, M. Y. Othman, S. A. Hj. Sulaiman, M. A. Md Wazir, and A. Azizan, "Determination of speed of sound using empirical equations and SVP," in 2011 IEEE 7th Int. Colloquium Signal Process. its Appl., pp. 252–256, 2011.
46. Akyildiz, Ian & Pompili, Dario & Melodia, Tommaso. (2005). Underwater Acoustic Sensor Networks: Research Challenges. *Ad Hoc Networks*. 3. 257-279. 10.1016/j.adhoc.2005.01.004.
47. S. Patil and S. Chaudhari, "DoS Attack Prevention Technique in Wireless Sensor Networks," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 79, pp. 715–721, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2016.03.094.
48. F. Al-Obaidy, N. Razfar, P. Moeini, and F. Mohammadi, "Wireless Positioning Network Location Prediction Based on Machine Learning Techniques," *IEEE Canadian Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering(CCECE)*, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1109/ccece47787.2020.9255727.
49. S. Wang, L. Chen, H. Hu, Z. Xue, and W. Pan, "Underwater Localization and Environment Mapping Using Wireless Robots," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 70, no. 3, pp. 1147–1170, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s11277-013-1106-z
50. A. Stefanov and M. Stojanovic, "Design and Performance Analysis of Underwater Acoustic Networks," *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 29, no. 10, pp. 2012–2021, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.1109/jsac.2011.111211.

Appendix

Dataset 1: solving UWSL using Cayley-Menger determinant

Bacon Nodes (from six different position)	Actual Sensor Nodes			Predicted Sensor Nodes			Distance Error From Original Position
	x	y	z	x	y	z	
Iteration 1: Beacon A1: [-14.56229 15.0054735 50.] Beacon A2: [16.33771 110.1054735 50.] Beacon A3: [-95.46229 73.7054735 50.] Beacon A4: [-95.46229 - 43.6945265 50.] Beacon A5: [16.33771 - 80.0945265 50.] Beacon A6: [85.43771 15.0054735 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	59.905145 07	0	0.094
	S3	85	95	0	85.02114 558	94.794824 88	0.226
Iteration 2: Beacon A1: [14.29145975 6.43506638 50.] Beacon A2: [45.19145975 101.53506638 50.] Beacon A3: [-66.60854025 65.13506638 50.] Beacon A4: [-66.60854025 - 52.26493362 50.] Beacon A5: [45.19145975 - 88.66493362 50.] Beacon A6: [114.29145975 6.43506638 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	59.868962 35	0	0.131
	S3	85	95	0	84.90213 194	94.888115 49	0.209
Iteration 3: Beacon A1: [-18.85213143 14.25915817 50.] Beacon A2: [12.04786857 109.35915817 50.] Beacon A3: [-99.75213143 72.95915817 50.] Beacon A4: [-99.75213143 - 44.44084183 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	59.962821 36	0	0.037
	S3	85	95	0	85.07013 567	94.930273 89	0.139

Beacon A5: [12.04786857 - 80.84084183 50.] Beacon A6: [81.14786857 14.25915817 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Iteration 4: Beacon A1: [-8.96753122 13.35208703 50.] Beacon A2: [21.93246878 108.45208703 50.] Beacon A3: [-89.86753122 72.05208703 50.] Beacon A4: [-89.86753122 - 45.34791297 50.] Beacon A5: [21.93246878 - 81.74791297 50.] Beacon A6: [91.03246878 13.35208703 50.]	S2	0	60	0	60.056230 5	0	0.056
	S3	85	95	0	85.14142 182	94.953301 42	0.188
Iteration 5: Beacon A1: [10.97984633 11.81960684 50.] Beacon A2: [41.87984633 106.91960684 50.] Beacon A3: [-69.92015367 70.51960684 50.] Beacon A4: [-69.92015367 - 46.88039316 50.] Beacon A5: [41.87984633 - 83.28039316 50.] Beacon A6: [110.97984633 11.81960684 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	59.991261 62	0	0.009
	S3	85	95	0	85.00456 343	94.970835 45	0.034
Iteration 6: Beacon A1: [12.0098469 3.05646959 50.] Beacon A2: [42.9098469 98.15646959 50.] Beacon A3: [-68.8901531 61.75646959 50.] Beacon A4: [-68.8901531 - 55.64353041 50.] Beacon A5: [42.9098469 - 92.04353041 50.] Beacon A6: [112.0098469 3.05646959 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	59.957362 01	0	0.043
	S3	85	95	0	84.82657 299	95.007914 37	0.181
Iteration 7:	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Beacon A1: [-11.7527445 - 8.94395776 50.] Beacon A2: [19.3472555 86.15604224 50.] Beacon A3: [-92.6527445 49.75604224 50.] Beacon A4: [-92.6527445 - 67.64395776 50.] Beacon A5: [19.1472555 - 104.04395776 50.] Beacon A6: [88.2472555 - 8.94395776 50.]	S2	0	60	0	0	60.059436	0	0.059
	S3	85	95	0	85.10558 721	95.105722 24	0	0.211
Iteration 8: Beacon A1: [11.57924496 5.88881958 50.] Beacon A2: [42.47924496 100.98881958 50.] Beacon A3: [-69.32075504 64.58881958 50.] Beacon A4: [-69.32075504 - 52.8118042 50.] Beacon A5: [42.47924496 - 89.2118042 50.] Beacon A6: [111.57924496 5.88881958 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	0	60.049693 25	0	0.05
	S3	85	95	0	84.90637 21	95.105203 22	0	0.199
Iteration 9: Beacon A1: [14.20133655 - 4.93923051 50.] Beacon A2: [45.10133655 90.16076949 50.] Beacon A3: [-66.69866345 53.76076949 50.] Beacon A4: [-66.69866345 - 63.63923051 50.] Beacon A5: [45.10133655 - 100.03923051 50.] Beacon A6: [114.20133655 - 4.93923051 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	0	60.006803 71	0	0.007
	S3	85	95	0	84.95112 309	95.217181 18	0	0.266
Iteration 10: Beacon A1: [10.22198463 11.60421927 50.] Beacon A2: [41.12198463 106.70421927 50.] Beacon A3: [-70.67801537 70.30421927 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	0	59.772260 12	0	0.228
	S3	85	95	0	84.99440 233	94.873235 69	0	0.132

Beacon A4: [-70.67801537 - 47.09578073 50.] Beacon A5: [41.12198463 - 83.49578073 50.] Beacon A6: [110.22198463 11.60421927 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Iteration 11: Beacon A1: [14.97742123 15.51346543 50.] Beacon A2: [45.87742123 110.61346543 50.] Beacon A3: [-65.92257877 74.21346543 50.] Beacon A4: [-65.92257877 - 43.18653457 50.] Beacon A5: [45.87742123 - 79.58653457 50.] Beacon A6: [114.97742123 15.51346543 50.]	S2	0	60	0	0	60.132962 7	0	0.133
	S3	85	95	0	85.02241 59	95.157140 88	0	0.18
Iteration 12: Beacon A1: [19.29962994 5.0165093 50.] Beacon A2: [50.19962994 100.1165093 50.] Beacon A3: [-61.60037006 63.7165093 50.] Beacon A4: [-61.60037006 - 53.6834907 50.] Beacon A5: [50.19962994 - 90.0834907 50.] Beacon A6: [119.29962994 5.0165093 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	0	59.768199 5	0	0.232
	S3	85	95	0	84.87590 24	94.735871 54	0	0.388
Iteration 13: Beacon A1: [10.77418936 19.21961555 50.] Beacon A2: [41.67418936 114.31961555 50.] Beacon A3: [-70.12581064 77.91961555 50.] Beacon A4: [-70.12581064 - 39.48038445 50.] Beacon A5: [41.67418936 - 75.88038445 50.]	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	0	59.985532 55	0	0.014
	S3	85	95	0	84.87875 165	95.241419 74	0	0.363

Beacon A6: [110.77418936 19.21961555 50.]																				
Iteration 14: Beacon A1: [-11.03421706 12.55173169 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [19.86578294 107.65173169 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.961353	0	0.039											
Beacon A3: [-91.93421706 71.25173169 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.01629 294	94.933888 71	0	0.082											
Beacon A4: [-91.93421706 - 46.14826831 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [19.86578294 - 82.54826831 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [88.96578294 12.55173169 50.]																				
Iteration 15: Beacon A1: [-2.09670373 14.32643342 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [28.80329627 109.42643342 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.935735 99	0	0.064											
Beacon A3: [-82.99670373 73.02643342 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.99762 02	94.816893 22	0	0.185											
Beacon A4: [-82.99670373 - 44.37356658 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [28.80329627 - 80.77356658 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [97.90329627 14.32643342 50.]																				
Iteration 16: Beacon A1: [1.78251085 11.05261936 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [32.68251085 106.15261936 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.988110 56	0	0.012											
Beacon A3: [-79.11748915 69.75261936 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.03309 149	95.095609 42	0	0.129											
Beacon A4: [-79.11748915 - 47.64738064 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [32.68251085 - 84.04738064 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [101.78251085 11.05261936 50.]																				
Iteration 17: Beacon A1: [13.99321309 - 3.43787919 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.199471 27	0	0.199											

Beacon A5: [49.55749095 - 83.04065422 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [118.65749095 12.05934578 50.]																				
Iteration 21: Beacon A1: [-4.72608644 - 0.98656059 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [26.17391356 94.11343941 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.343417 07	0	0.343											
Beacon A3: [-85.62608644 57.71343941 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.14488 759	95.151604 09	0	0.296											
Beacon A4: [-85.62608644 - 59.68656059 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [26.17391356 - 96.08656059 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [95.27391356 - 0.98656059 50.]																				
Iteration 22: Beacon A1: [12.72143586 10.13023469 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [43.62143586 105.23023469 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.874162 77	0	0.126											
Beacon A3: [-68.17856414 68.83023469 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.08438 447	94.890666 98	0	0.194											
Beacon A4: [-68.17856414 - 48.56976351 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [43.62143586 - 84.96976351 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [112.72143586 10.13023469 50.]																				
Iteration 23: Beacon A1: [19.95501236 - 6.11023651 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [50.95501236 88.98976349 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.913144 44	0	0.087											
Beacon A3: [-60.94498764 52.58976349 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.10019 265	94.997935 68	0	0.102											
Beacon A4: [-60.94498764 - 64.81023651 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [50.95501236 - 101.21023651 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [119.95501236 - 6.11023651 50.]																				
Iteration 24: Beacon A1: [13.37114825 - 12.10240759 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Beacon A2: [44.89321309 91.66212081 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.12607 674	95.104096 87	0	0.23											
Beacon A3: [-66.90678691 55.26212081 50.]																				
Beacon A4: [-66.90678691 - 62.13787919 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [44.89321309 - 98.53787919 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [113.99321309 - 3.43787919 50.]																				
Iteration 18: Beacon A1: [7.6713124 1.99572839 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [38.5713124 97.09572839 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.123500 2	0	0.124											
Beacon A3: [-73.2286876 60.69572839 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.15371 038	94.990400 55	0	0.163											
Beacon A4: [-73.2286876 - 56.70427161 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [38.5713124 - 93.10427161 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [107.6713124 1.99572839 50.]																				
Iteration 19: Beacon A1: [-18.89093506 - 8.39419008 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [12.00906494 86.70580992 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.960916 06	0	0.039											
Beacon A3: [-99.79093506 50.30580992 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.94569 129	95.026484 68	0	0.081											
Beacon A4: [-99.79093506 - 67.09419008 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [12.00906494 - 103.49419008 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [81.10906494 - 8.39419008 50.]																				
Iteration 20: Beacon A1: [18.65749095 12.05934578 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [49.55749095 107.15934578 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.981436 91	0	0.019											
Beacon A3: [-62.24250905 70.75934578 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.09322 664	94.867103 65	0	0.226											
Beacon A4: [-62.24250905 - 46.64065422 50.]																				

Beacon A1: [13.37114825 - 12.10240759 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.981567 69	0	0.018											
Beacon A2: [44.27114825 82.99759241 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.90410 11	95.148071 18	0	0.244											
Beacon A3: [-67.52885175 46.59759241 50.]																				
Beacon A4: [-67.52885175 - 70.80240759 50.]																				
Beacon A5: [44.27114825 - 107.20240759 50.]																				
Beacon A6: [113.37114825 - 12.10240759 50.]																				
Iteration 25: Beacon A1: [-17.31132767 - 5.43601194 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Beacon A2: [13.58867233 89.66398806 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.875572 0	0	0.124											
Beacon A3: [-98.21132767 53.26398806 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.04035 702	94.796536 74	0	0.244											
Beacon A4: [-98.21132767 - 64.13601194 50.]																				

Beacon A4: [-64.85705712 - 75.24593672 50.] Beacon A5: [46.94294288 - 111.64593672 50.] Beacon A6: [116.04294288 - 16.54593672 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
Iteration 28: Beacon A1: [-17.86109463 19.79677922 50.] Beacon A2: [13.03890537 114.89677922 50.] Beacon A3: [-98.76109463 78.49677922 50.] Beacon A4: [-98.76109463 - 38.90322078 50.] Beacon A5: [13.03890537 - 75.30322078 50.] Beacon A6: [82.13890537 19.79677922 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.9018855	0	0.098
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.05351566	94.86039247	0	0.193
Iteration 29: Beacon A1: [-6.4739636 6.83089711 50.] Beacon A2: [24.4260364 101.93089711 50.] Beacon A3: [-87.3739636 65.53089711 50.] Beacon A4: [-87.3739636 - 51.86910289 50.] Beacon A5: [24.4260364 - 88.26910289 50.] Beacon A6: [93.5260364 6.83089711 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.98707683	0	0.013
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.01736577	94.9656763	0	0.052
Iteration 30: Beacon A1: [15.13573831 - 10.64494147 50.] Beacon A2: [46.03573831 84.45505853 50.] Beacon A3: [-65.76426169 48.05505853 50.] Beacon A4: [-65.76426169 - 69.34494147 50.] Beacon A5: [46.03573831 - 105.74494147 50.] Beacon A6: [115.13573831 - 10.64494147 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.8285518	0	0.171
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.98647015	94.91978118	0	0.094

Beacon A3: [-83.55575693 55.24693489 50.] Beacon A4: [-83.55575693 - 62.15306511 50.] Beacon A5: [28.24424307 - 98.55306511 50.] Beacon A6: [97.34424307 - 3.45306511 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
Iteration 35: Beacon A1: [-5.38023045 - 2.00331664 50.] Beacon A2: [25.51976955 93.09668336 50.] Beacon A3: [-86.28023045 56.69668336 50.] Beacon A4: [-86.28023045 - 60.70331664 50.] Beacon A5: [25.51976955 - 97.10331664 50.] Beacon A6: [94.61976955 - 2.00331664 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.87064615	0	0.129
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.76078684	95.04911024	0	0.288
Iteration 36: Beacon A1: [-15.39738664 - 9.9246515 50.] Beacon A2: [46.29738664 85.1753485 50.] Beacon A3: [-65.50261336 48.7753485 50.] Beacon A4: [-65.50261336 - 68.6346515 50.] Beacon A5: [46.29738664 - 105.0246515 50.] Beacon A6: [115.39738664 - 9.9246515 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.00491666	0	0.005
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.87219725	95.09458359	0	0.222
Iteration 37: Beacon A1: [19.12366349 - 16.22054015 50.] Beacon A2: [50.02366349 78.87945985 50.] Beacon A3: [-61.77633651 42.47945985 50.] Beacon A4: [-61.77633651 - 74.92054015 50.] Beacon A5: [50.02366349 - 111.32054015 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.93531095	0	0.065
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.0044854	94.92721611	0	0.077

Iteration 31: Beacon A1: [-14.51410925 - 19.52351802 50.] Beacon A2: [16.38589075 75.57648198 50.] Beacon A3: [-95.41410925 39.17648198 50.] Beacon A4: [-95.41410925 - 78.22351802 50.] Beacon A5: [16.38589075 - 114.62351802 50.] Beacon A6: [85.48589075 - 19.52351802 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.21991171	0	0.22
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.14619029	95.08358369	0	0.23
Iteration 32: Beacon A1: [-14.10875176 15.03499448 50.] Beacon A2: [16.79124824 110.13499448 50.] Beacon A3: [-95.00875176 73.73499448 50.] Beacon A4: [-95.00875176 - 43.66500552 50.] Beacon A5: [16.79124824 - 80.06500552 50.] Beacon A6: [85.89124824 15.03499448 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.12167359	0	0.122
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.96637238	95.02057856	0	0.054
Iteration 33: Beacon A1: [3.37237815 - 7.02661611 50.] Beacon A2: [34.27237815 88.07338389 50.] Beacon A3: [-77.52762185 51.67338389 50.] Beacon A4: [-77.52762185 - 65.72661611 50.] Beacon A5: [34.27237815 - 102.12661611 50.] Beacon A6: [103.37237815 - 7.02661611 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.81055632	0	0.189
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.85023046	94.93396922	0	0.216
Iteration 34: Beacon A1: [-2.65575693 - 3.45306511 50.] Beacon A2: [28.24424307 91.64693489 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.26627186	0	0.266
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.11272999	95.28379233	0	0.397

Beacon A6: [119.12366349 - 16.22054015 50.]									
Iteration 38: Beacon A1: [-7.75846987 0.45795983 50.] Beacon A2: [23.14153013 95.55795983 50.] Beacon A3: [-88.65846987 59.15795983 50.] Beacon A4: [-88.65846987 - 58.24204017 50.] Beacon A5: [23.14153013 - 94.64204017 50.] Beacon A6: [92.24153013 0.45795983 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.07518704	0	0.075
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.05249866	95.05324158	0	0.106
Iteration 39: Beacon A1: [5.61895954 0.61357011 50.] Beacon A2: [36.51895954 95.71357011 50.] Beacon A3: [-75.28104046 59.31357011 50.] Beacon A4: [-75.28104046 - 58.08642989 50.] Beacon A5: [36.51895954 - 94.48642989 50.] Beacon A6: [105.61895954 0.61357011 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.23286257	0	0.233
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.07690666	95.13904292	0	0.216
Iteration 40: Beacon A1: [18.14581974 2.75995053 50.] Beacon A2: [49.04581974 97.85995053 50.] Beacon A3: [-62.75418026 61.45995053 50.] Beacon A4: [-62.75418026 - 55.94004947 50.] Beacon A5: [49.04581974 - 92.34004947 50.] Beacon A6: [118.14581974 2.75995053 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.65451443	0	0.345
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.87282	94.65427701	0	0.473
Iteration 41: Beacon A1: [-0.15053407 - 15.73670118 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.85458664	0	0.145

Beacon A2: [30.74946593 - 79.36329882 50.] Beacon A3: [-81.05053407 - 42.96329882 50.] Beacon A4: [-81.05053407 - 74.43670118 50.] Beacon A5: [30.74946593 - 110.83670118 50.] Beacon A6: [99.84946593 - 15.73670118 50.]	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.90216863	94.91011136	0	0.188
Iteration 42: Beacon A1: [8.20893879 - 12.07407116 50.] Beacon A2: [39.10893879 - 107.17407116 50.] Beacon A3: [-72.69106121 - 70.77407116 50.] Beacon A4: [-72.69106121 - 46.62592884 50.] Beacon A5: [39.10893879 - 83.02592884 50.] Beacon A6: [108.20893879 - 12.07407116 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.19268744	0	0.193
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.9754487	95.28526324	0	0.31
Iteration 43: Beacon A1: [-1.70059205 - 18.82071681 50.] Beacon A2: [29.19940795 - 113.92071681 50.] Beacon A3: [-82.60059205 - 77.52071681 50.] Beacon A4: [-82.60059205 - 39.87928319 50.] Beacon A5: [29.19940795 - 76.27928319 50.] Beacon A6: [98.29940795 - 18.82071681 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.05379979	0	0.054
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.0022387	95.02718234	0	0.029
Iteration 44: Beacon A1: [-17.76305815 - 17.08750052 50.] Beacon A2: [13.13694185 - 112.18750052 50.] Beacon A3: [-98.66305815 - 75.78750052 50.] Beacon A4: [-98.66305815 - 41.61249948 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.9234556	0	0.077
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.92638687	95.04390277	0	0.118

Beacon A5: [13.13694185 - 78.01249948 50.] Beacon A6: [82.23694185 - 17.08750052 50.]									
Iteration 45: Beacon A1: [13.80708189 - 3.44579377 50.] Beacon A2: [44.70708189 - 91.65420623 50.] Beacon A3: [-67.09291811 - 55.25420623 50.] Beacon A4: [-67.09291811 - 62.14579377 50.] Beacon A5: [44.70708189 - 98.54579377 50.] Beacon A6: [113.80708189 - 3.44579377 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.15162123	0	0.152
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.02803148	95.02899006	0	0.057
Iteration 46: Beacon A1: [2.11720527 - 18.06388924 50.] Beacon A2: [33.01720527 - 77.03611076 50.] Beacon A3: [-78.78279473 - 40.63611076 50.] Beacon A4: [-78.78279473 - 76.76388924 50.] Beacon A5: [33.01720527 - 113.16388924 50.] Beacon A6: [102.11720527 - 18.06388924 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.94999817	0	0.05
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.01808774	94.88568735	0	0.132
Iteration 47: Beacon A1: [-2.32382002 - 16.04505456 50.] Beacon A2: [28.57617998 - 79.05494544 50.] Beacon A3: [-83.22382002 - 42.65494544 50.] Beacon A4: [-83.22382002 - 74.74505456 50.] Beacon A5: [28.57617998 - 111.14505456 50.] Beacon A6: [97.67617998 - 16.04505456 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.81272168	0	0.187
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.85505155	95.03537408	0	0.18
Iteration 48:	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0

Beacon A1: [0.13333662 - 18.48433657 50.] Beacon A2: [31.03333662 - 76.61566343 50.] Beacon A3: [-80.76666338 - 40.21566343 50.] Beacon A4: [-80.76666338 - 77.18433657 50.] Beacon A5: [31.03333662 - 113.58433657 50.] Beacon A6: [100.13333662 - 18.48433657 50.]	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.03706631	0	0.037
	S3	85	95	0	S3	85.18264179	94.80351819	0	0.379
Iteration 49: Beacon A1: [0.24377193 - 4.18994034 50.] Beacon A2: [31.14377193 - 90.91005966 50.] Beacon A3: [-80.65622807 - 54.51005966 50.] Beacon A4: [-80.65622807 - 62.88994034 50.] Beacon A5: [31.14377193 - 99.28994034 50.] Beacon A6: [100.24377193 - 4.18994034 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	60.00806171	0	0.008
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.90302957	95.02375369	0	0.121
Iteration 50: Beacon A1: [-6.87580607 - 15.44080493 50.] Beacon A2: [24.02419393 - 110.54080493 50.] Beacon A3: [-87.77580607 - 74.14080493 50.] Beacon A4: [-87.77580607 - 43.25919507 50.] Beacon A5: [24.02419393 - 79.65919507 50.] Beacon A6: [93.12419393 - 15.44080493 50.]	S1	0	0	0	S1	0	0	0	0
	S2	0	60	0	S2	0	59.95983617	0	0.04
	S3	85	95	0	S3	84.96536369	95.06474026	0	0.099

Dataset 2: Underwater sensor movements due to ocean current

Iteration	Beacon	Distance to S1	Distance to S2	Distance to S3
1	A1	49.97306234	77.46082409	138.2434649
	A2	111.776828	68.6953222	73.76529663
	A3	111.7478016	94.15828303	177.478463
	A4	111.3801251	151.750847	232.3545286
	A5	112.69029	166.5698134	204.4640773
	A6	112.6575084	127.9571997	107.9288507
2	A1	50.86522009	77.71316078	138.0678961
	A2	111.076812	67.47835619	74.67516458
	A3	111.8895518	94.78546084	177.8071947
	A4	111.5807186	151.6083902	233.4541234
	A5	111.8120545	165.0457912	205.3176261
	A6	110.9323384	126.6133236	109.0975386
3	A1	50.25292777	77.54964547	138.0988594
	A2	111.7185043	69.48197408	74.00530061

	A4	112.2002624	151.6556575	235.7036086
	A5	110.9746753	165.8410746	207.577056
	A6	111.4882866	127.1068671	110.87367
9	A1	49.75670498	78.20324724	142.70441
	A2	110.4981327	68.53306845	76.66095986
	A3	112.1836425	96.01079531	181.3552231
	A4	112.1435071	151.7604912	237.4598153
	A5	112.2184891	165.4860983	207.8827686
	A6	111.3565886	127.5328684	112.1919941
10	A1	49.91896584	78.13635231	143.998072
	A2	111.8255809	68.0436924	75.78096956
	A3	112.3538443	95.18564394	181.3558574
	A4	112.0958803	152.102939	237.8939126
	A5	111.665923	165.473959	209.2291226
	A6	112.1654803	126.7403392	111.1156331
11	A1	49.88839543	78.28717597	143.6275283
	A2	112.2164449	68.97214389	76.45827578
	A3	112.4660881	94.75364472	182.2014272
	A4	111.5637398	151.7302944	239.2854516
	A5	112.2336796	166.0989336	210.149563
	A6	111.8824155	127.573145	112.2532567
12	A1	49.12668294	78.5628865	143.5879241
	A2	111.8755259	68.57773223	76.49823738
	A3	112.2086367	95.14355371	181.9772935
	A4	111.9001042	153.1182571	238.455983
	A5	111.9730662	165.8834591	210.0306912
	A6	112.2650178	126.7978989	112.4130191
13	A1	49.82781379	78.75547724	144.1606616
	A2	112.474988	69.15320848	77.51361415
	A3	111.2752942	95.51849118	182.524571
	A4	112.8138577	151.9855754	239.298593

	A3	112.0035703	94.71830667	179.2449731	
	A4	110.9284002	152.516342	233.3198544	
	A5	112.0583509	165.2726836	204.2409031	
	A6	111.6485909	126.9288614	108.7483882	
	4	A1	49.78793523	78.09609813	139.4771172
		A2	110.8821262	67.94609805	74.4192373
A3		111.8286416	94.97579287	178.7079845	
A4		111.4885861	151.1450223	234.3264508	
A5		112.2494741	165.8627851	206.6051507	
A6		111.9049992	127.5006231	109.5165307	
5	A1	49.87111044	78.01356084	139.3662438	
	A2	111.3870772	69.15474138	75.55220098	
	A3	110.7270664	95.57884754	179.0407924	
	A4	112.0691385	152.3319419	235.4065525	
	A5	111.963669	165.7218587	206.9681259	
	A6	110.811686	127.2409432	109.8390317	
6	A1	51.36260208	77.8895247	140.490366	
	A2	112.1405095	68.41703106	75.36609852	
	A3	111.9986208	95.42738062	180.0962679	
	A4	111.187551	152.4492175	235.9739961	
	A5	110.3736392	165.7745321	207.2050125	
	A6	111.0004834	127.2022679	111.0580466	
7	A1	49.67926081	78.91359072	141.6168233	
	A2	112.5998006	68.32150751	75.5802092	
	A3	110.6350599	95.49683429	180.0432738	
	A4	112.9179742	152.5903715	235.6029033	
	A5	111.5429401	165.4595138	207.0788048	
	A6	111.5670698	126.0641112	111.4810247	
8	A1	49.69469792	77.96975369	142.4385442	
	A2	111.21579	67.93084666	76.39443942	
	A3	111.4975672	94.08864873	179.7896667	

14	A5	112.2210671	166.0417123	210.8442598
	A6	112.1102746	127.0456664	113.5721804
	A1	49.54542488	78.14469209	144.4359804
	A2	111.0992095	68.77784233	78.49395546
	A3	111.3664626	95.32202317	183.7428659
	A4	112.0875403	152.6110842	240.0626577
15	A5	111.8789286	165.3438469	211.1317339
	A6	111.5657698	126.9416976	113.7781436
	A1	50.0497614	78.23508052	145.789171
	A2	111.0390954	68.12342605	78.09603715
	A3	111.0209064	95.24823117	183.3663535
	A4	112.6852161	152.1296464	240.689674
16	A5	111.1881267	166.5986055	211.1405796
	A6	111.4636313	126.5174704	113.6295273
	A1	50.34039883	78.22366813	145.6461334
	A2	111.2121382	68.44078638	78.55993198
	A3	111.1465428	94.61856868	183.4805723
	A4	111.5164999	152.283382	241.5266849
17	A5	111.8687484	165.541254	212.6589469
	A6	111.5136505	127.3400425	114.6073779
	A1	50.54693628	78.94227191	147.4304496
	A2	111.5232481	69.06133751	79.01333853
	A3	111.9409105	94.93827275	184.478096
	A4	111.2293129	152.0746232	241.3405699
18	A5	111.9283202	166.036921	212.1157818
	A6	111.8569464	126.4826841	114.7090755
	A1	50.63976879	78.50432822	147.0286518
	A2	111.4907163	68.28814526	79.69567061
	A3	111.046761	95.04891912	185.5686213
	A4	112.2252059	152.0744889	242.4190981
A5	111.4465721	165.5818854	213.2975601	

24	A1	49.6983571	78.54183526	150.8181612
	A2	111.9503254	67.94368157	82.32146719
	A3	111.0948019	95.72039079	187.7058083
	A4	111.0012798	152.8091733	245.8626548
	A5	111.0564956	165.7315761	217.3707932
	A6	111.5159779	126.6640621	117.3072949
25	A1	49.67034036	77.41482313	151.3834187
	A2	111.8034637	67.55275586	82.14939491
	A3	112.2272189	94.37137755	188.516096
	A4	111.5987541	151.8265566	245.9497777
	A5	111.7954414	166.1100245	218.6044937
	A6	112.7935171	127.3825613	117.6344838
26	A1	48.95893905	77.67022747	152.191874
	A2	111.6748539	68.65496186	81.90966978
	A3	111.4455316	94.61618499	189.1204933
	A4	112.0684131	152.1738052	247.1760842
	A5	112.5486292	166.2248017	218.7733424
	A6	112.0882243	126.7944923	117.7504661
27	A1	50.28195834	77.54860773	152.3002612
	A2	112.3429923	68.60496205	82.27757191
	A3	111.2821759	94.83555049	190.2232914
	A4	112.2569647	152.0220878	247.7479892
	A5	111.390559	165.6323966	219.2155251
	A6	111.6224757	127.368648	118.6904297
28	A1	49.96662655	77.56368787	153.5812365
	A2	111.9603586	67.86576136	83.34605348
	A3	112.1305899	94.95676776	190.46102
	A4	111.6766979	151.6245093	247.9961729
	A5	112.1308739	166.3648626	219.0438356
	A6	111.5440939	127.1927719	119.1575535
29	A1	50.17776016	78.10902059	153.0334879

19	A6	112.3980132	126.6315733	114.9135733
	A1	49.75862644	77.83591769	148.4602924
	A2	112.204914	68.5529854	79.07772128
	A3	111.8097742	93.85503841	186.9496555
	A4	112.102073	153.2479603	242.8950411
	A5	112.0979068	166.4147992	214.6418587
20	A6	111.5718375	126.4654848	115.0683924
	A1	50.37146788	78.66003518	148.1148969
	A2	111.9353535	67.8298072	80.67105347
	A3	112.8786765	94.74031564	187.3391182
	A4	111.2128823	152.7505944	243.3698577
	A5	112.4984514	166.0625699	214.7294787
21	A6	111.0806606	126.9323935	115.6196173
	A1	49.78798489	78.47882805	149.5104631
	A2	110.914061	68.18725318	80.96594544
	A3	111.8870884	95.56864963	186.9556718
	A4	112.0251702	151.6465315	244.4553249
	A5	111.4429592	166.6981931	214.7839447
22	A6	112.1742027	127.0509231	116.1233675
	A1	49.90355988	77.95630546	150.3791856
	A2	112.1462772	69.26957157	80.90035104
	A3	110.8731718	95.51407468	187.8442368
	A4	112.7872886	152.3241753	243.8090938
	A5	112.0858359	165.9882573	215.6773063
23	A6	111.4284363	127.3223135	116.7149183
	A1	50.07045378	78.27618779	150.4579178
	A2	111.69486	66.68632889	80.95601355
	A3	111.8696654	94.97808914	188.6582794
	A4	111.7194241	152.5188656	245.0776329
	A5	111.3932276	166.9535222	216.0657992
A6	111.85773	125.7774447	117.205538	

30	A2	112.1286464	68.80317043	84.50589254
	A3	111.0216183	94.94869202	191.0425453
	A4	111.7114599	152.2368244	248.1183026
	A5	112.1136909	166.2725078	219.6223118
	A6	110.9704456	126.5159628	119.6423531
	31	A1	49.05668764	78.0765508
A2		112.2345297	69.3486179	83.43545428
A3		111.435809	95.30215016	191.6840736
A4		112.3215904	153.005862	248.3646642
A5		112.5147117	165.1944966	221.0454139
A6		111.4429695	127.0716643	119.8952411
32	A1	50.92595219	78.10207021	154.7516098
	A2	111.7324807	68.15033004	83.58608739
	A3	111.4686163	95.4510873	191.7088924
	A4	112.8174682	151.7461469	249.7303378
	A5	111.0914138	166.2561509	221.1951044
	A6	112.4861195	126.8870997	120.1561587
33	A1	49.80891409	78.30333814	155.5181338
	A2	112.5300041	68.367831	84.86010781
	A3	111.6265569	94.38980566	192.4628929
	A4	112.1603538	151.6476627	250.6985231
	A5	111.6651163	166.0459176	221.5412433
	A6	111.2739732	126.6459139	120.5053524
34	A1	50.42854648	78.20695415	156.0506209
	A2	112.1219116	68.36759988	85.84511658
	A3	111.283279	95.90138011	193.4113012
	A4	111.9427982	152.383835	251.168513
	A5	111.481032	165.8619916	221.8411074
	A6	111.0517566	126.6609103	120.9908738
35	A1	50.55911595	78.62768163	156.3945372
	A2	112.5246346	68.96811198	85.48785231

	A3	111.7855755	94.75496058	193.3750185
	A4	111.766787	152.7217683	251.5802739
	A5	111.126999	166.5312	222.9765502
	A6	112.8191434	126.9423303	122.2200568
35	A1	50.28933486	78.86550975	157.4438441
	A2	111.3457305	68.84290901	86.62368705
	A3	111.3906407	95.19617813	194.1138579
	A4	111.4445241	152.2316898	252.3158812
	A5	112.2200071	165.4661971	223.6914574
	A6	112.2616775	126.7764227	121.0311588
36	A1	50.2756943	78.37864412	158.49878
	A2	112.5238023	67.62901241	86.67823965
	A3	111.649854	95.31675688	194.868368
	A4	112.4216776	152.1381731	253.4539429
	A5	111.7086372	165.6689957	223.9955316
	A6	112.2382901	127.2322297	122.0522882
37	A1	50.2349621	78.1410033	159.2447519
	A2	111.3669439	68.11666275	87.63081139
	A3	111.9061473	94.94031606	194.9464918
	A4	111.7266733	151.4023207	254.0342163
	A5	111.3297064	165.9378078	224.1825856
	A6	112.085578	126.8941038	122.0522386
38	A1	49.94136172	78.56256434	159.083366
	A2	111.5230751	68.47878206	87.9148364
	A3	111.3446239	93.29094363	195.8083112
	A4	111.4473752	151.8009892	254.2712416
	A5	112.1316819	165.1232726	225.0356798
	A6	111.1791389	127.1512268	122.6367953
39	A1	50.23692887	77.5220947	158.9403254
	A2	112.2482491	68.96360248	87.32060854
	A3	111.1992165	94.7532382	195.3750601

	A5	112.7281009	166.0055649	227.4417065
	A6	112.529104	126.6579346	126.3780972
45	A1	49.75397333	77.47248053	163.1396722
	A2	110.3861142	69.48387507	90.50065454
	A3	112.3311024	95.28993174	198.3771165
	A4	111.7850946	151.9986188	258.8579191
	A5	110.9075112	166.7235951	227.2699707
	A6	111.8213881	127.1209588	126.1369835
46	A1	49.85142953	78.10821852	163.2907191
	A2	112.0323259	69.19019651	90.68501885
	A3	111.1006792	95.54870944	199.9346317
	A4	111.5608216	153.1281134	258.9002513
	A5	112.9103686	165.8369015	229.1732622
	A6	112.2826012	126.8673427	126.7963966
47	A1	49.53651235	78.61226187	163.2915621
	A2	111.9532587	68.48778075	90.42987417
	A3	111.2689045	94.3562962	200.2774485
	A4	111.0130924	152.9087686	259.6592192
	A5	111.6318719	166.1800043	229.2462441
	A6	111.9907973	126.1479714	127.6896862
48	A1	49.76289627	78.73705053	165.3020755
	A2	110.4345539	67.92365383	91.50416941
	A3	112.0364579	95.83582184	199.7454977
	A4	112.4765548	153.1885227	259.8564029
	A5	112.9722236	165.1910682	230.0620157
	A6	111.8957964	127.0200054	127.1622276
49	A1	50.42575853	77.83883957	165.5771911
	A2	111.5561597	68.3887571	92.00673755
	A3	110.7811917	95.21816628	201.1493979
	A4	111.470884	152.6501617	260.0277089
	A5	111.5728587	165.6726424	230.3587945

	A4	112.6479372	151.3340867	255.2702286
	A5	111.4439261	166.2329555	225.5338426
	A6	111.4724816	126.7432028	123.3771687
40	A1	49.31466289	77.66454833	159.9915067
	A2	112.0120134	67.43832262	87.58355791
	A3	111.5395035	95.54569903	195.1449287
	A4	111.4395837	151.6533561	255.1799073
	A5	112.0338496	165.1028393	226.6596717
	A6	112.351623	126.4412918	124.5202674
41	A1	49.71434701	77.16523949	159.4160793
	A2	111.9680395	68.43940117	88.25026107
	A3	112.1792735	94.57887278	197.0918119
	A4	112.1006924	152.0020987	255.2816422
	A5	111.3119592	165.6378023	226.47705
	A6	110.892988	127.5691303	124.0091891
42	A1	50.17485613	77.63581813	160.4329027
	A2	111.5102368	68.30268021	88.93164915
	A3	111.2952271	95.29944648	197.7216982
	A4	112.143846	152.1430705	256.9801274
	A5	111.5083958	165.6968313	228.1083234
	A6	112.0035115	127.1129255	124.5131033
43	A1	50.5458726	77.62707558	161.9852405
	A2	112.5633932	68.87971995	88.60173779
	A3	112.3900354	94.43457588	197.340607
	A4	111.8596581	152.4053084	257.4751872
	A5	111.5735876	165.8365059	227.1599493
	A6	111.4492295	126.4015935	125.157495
44	A1	50.03762878	77.77390321	162.5746285
	A2	111.478588	68.66782371	90.11560354
	A3	110.9769686	95.18454995	199.1586654
	A4	111.1059805	151.5176602	257.7840065

	A6	112.3585768	127.1534373	127.4127179
50	A1	49.94035281	78.14962116	166.5676305
	A2	110.933598	68.89717504	92.35084422
	A3	111.4764377	95.34842406	201.6276009
	A4	112.1934952	152.527123	261.4073858
	A5	112.0713585	165.8738202	230.4347731
	A6	111.9302793	126.4957301	128.4086287

Dataset 3: Solving UWSL using Cayley-Menger determinant For Future Prediction

Iteration	S1_x	S1_y	S1_z	S2_x	S2_y	S2_z	S3_x	S3_y	S3_z
1	0	0	0	0	59.397 3037	0	86.816 5562	93.924 31145	0
2	0	0	0	0	57.734 53351	0	85.437 474	94.689 66465	0
3	0	0	0	0	59.118 11667	0	88.043 18773	94.685 09065	0
4	0	0	0	0	57.859 95115	0	85.992 77054	95.397 98126	0
5	0	0	0	0	56.601 33587	0	85.054 99489	94.267 68466	0
6	0	0	0	0	60.079 05186	0	86.715 49664	98.018 24604	0
7	0	0	0	0	60.970 91918	0	86.491 97802	99.815 17603	0
8	0	0	0	0	61.141 23738	0	89.013 85703	97.838 89522	0
9	0	0	0	0	57.389 04941	0	87.247 53861	97.092 74158	0
10	0	0	0	0	59.330 61554	0	88.219 17774	99.598 2869	0
11	0	0	0	0	58.488 03539	0	89.700 21429	99.049 36824	0
12	0	0	0	0	60.319 16488	0	89.231 16159	100.85 80638	0

13	0	0	0	0	59.625 52983	0	88.667 21688	101.22 36096	0
14	0	0	0	0	59.006 39861	0	90.472 05332	100.39 83179	0
15	0	0	0	0	61.488 45077	0	89.615 9107	103.19 07751	0
16	0	0	0	0	58.039 42177	0	90.248 09139	101.14 78785	0
17	0	0	0	0	60.721 41254	0	91.670 56907	103.88 48588	0
18	0	0	0	0	60.889 11714	0	92.005 05813	104.68 27865	0
19	0	0	0	0	62.346 49372	0	96.149 68502	103.59 66914	0
20	0	0	0	0	59.453 94869	0	94.938 49958	102.32 11335	0
21	0	0	0	0	61.192 08039	0	92.464 09546	106.27 08369	0
22	0	0	0	0	59.726 49368	0	93.975 85993	102.86 63713	0
23	0	0	0	0	64.394 57118	0	94.807 34139	109.92 06948	0
24	0	0	0	0	59.165 5943	0	91.654 8065	106.74 13381	0
25	0	0	0	0	60.973 09095	0	95.786 63616	107.13 08873	0
26	0	0	0	0	59.642 19687	0	95.694 27386	106.66 8831	0
27	0	0	0	0	59.723 64154	0	96.318 53124	106.24 24548	0
28	0	0	0	0	60.012 79748	0	96.438 5667	107.37 3593	0
29	0	0	0	0	60.375 63993	0	97.177 69919	107.58 01953	0

30	0	0	0	0	58.304 71728	0	97.586 24968	105.68 5073	0
31	0	0	0	0	61.894 2552	0	96.377 23923	111.28 85929	0
32	0	0	0	0	60.623 5438	0	98.972 82306	109.40 41856	0
33	0	0	0	0	59.523 19285	0	97.139 60557	109.58 17025	0
34	0	0	0	0	63.557 69089	0	99.386 61278	113.97 94185	0
35	0	0	0	0	58.625 8454	0	99.082 52642	110.20 11046	0
36	0	0	0	0	59.637 35215	0	98.986 54648	111.55 41342	0
37	0	0	0	0	60.255 18289	0	99.985 7642	112.51 4109	0
38	0	0	0	0	58.529 18063	0	103.97 01713	108.76 60375	0
39	0	0	0	0	60.250 26708	0	100.20 93416	113.19 91801	0
40	0	0	0	0	58.396 711	0	97.328 93811	115.57 11701	0
41	0	0	0	0	59.644 21554	0	103.45 85135	110.10 40824	0
42	0	0	0	0	59.351 95044	0	101.46 79519	113.86 77313	0
43	0	0	0	0	60.734 34002	0	103.01 01667	115.23 8456	0
44	0	0	0	0	60.162 75304	0	102.55 39872	117.30 60435	0
45	0	0	0	0	61.768 3367	0	102.82 70308	116.99 055	0
46	0	0	0	0	58.960 93394	0	103.01 92062	116.10 12573	0
47	0	0	0	0	62.553 65376	0	104.87 70827	119.77 84461	0
48	0	0	0	0	57.171 84214	0	102.63 40089	114.79 82284	0
49	0	0	0	0	60.274 41288	0	104.44 07893	117.37 75106	0
50	0	0	0	0	60.511 21184	0	105.05 52187	118.70 30914	0
51	0	0	0	0	63.305 71847	0	107.05 29449	121.23 62649	0